

OPTAIN

Optimal Strategies to Retain Water and Nutrients

SWAP Field-scale modelling protocol¹

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Abbreviations

AHC	Automatic hard calibration tool
ALFA	Fitting parameter of the soil water retention curve
CH	Crop Height
COUP	Coupled Heat and Mass Transfer Model
CS	Case Study
CSS	Case Study Site
DVS	Crop Development Stage
FC	Field capacity
GCM	Global Circulation Model
HBV	Hydrological model “Hydrologiska Byråns Vattenbalansavdelning”
HRU	Hydrological Response Units
INCA	Integrated Catchment Model
LAI	Leaf Area Index
LISEM	Limburg Soil Erosion Model
MIKE-SHE	Integrated hydrological modelling system developed by DHI
MHC	Manual hard calibration and visualisation tool
NPAR	Fitting parameter of the soil water retention curve
NSWRM	Natural/Small Water Retention Measures
K function	Soil hydraulic conductivity function ($K(\theta)$ or $K(h)$)
NSE	Nash-Sutcliffe model efficiency index
ORES	Residual water content
OSAT	Saturated water content
PBIAS	Percent of bias in model performance
pF-curve	Soil water retention curve ($\theta(h)$)
PTF	Pedotransfer function
PM	Penman-Monteith
R²	Coefficient of determination
RD	Rooting Depth
RETC	RETention Curve tool

RCM	Regional Climate Model
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathway
SCF	Soil Cover Fraction
SWAP	Soil Water Atmosphere Plant (model)
SWAT	Soil and Water Assessment Tool
SWC	Soil Water Content (θ)
TOPMODEL	Topography based Hydrological Model
VIC	Variable Infiltration Capacity model
VGM	Van Genuchten – Mualem model
WOFOST	WOrld FOod Studies
WP	Wilting point

1. Introduction

The primary objective of the EU H2020 OPTAIN project is to identify efficient and easy-to-implement Natural-/ Small Water Retention Measures (NSWRMs) and optimize their spatial allocation and combination for retaining and reusing water and nutrients in small agricultural catchments across boreal, continental, and Pannonian regions of Europe.

To achieve this objective, OPTAIN considers two different scales. Soil and Water Assessment Tool+ (SWAT+) catchment-scale model is being used for simulating water and nutrient transport processes at sub-catchment level. Such models use simplified approaches for describing the soil water regime at profile- or field scales, and the calculated values are usually not verified or tested. This also raises the question on how precisely SWAT+ can simulate the effects of different management measures on water regime and plant development at field-scale.

Soil hydrological models, like the Soil Water Atmosphere Plant model (SWAP) are commonly run from profile- up to field-scales. These models focus on the soil water regime and believed to be more precise in describing water transport in the soil-water-atmosphere system. Also, the soil input data of these models allows incorporation of management practices in the modelling procedure in a more exact way. Thus, the outputs of such models can be used as references for larger scale models such as SWAT+.

The main goals of applying a field-scale model in the OPTAIN project are i) to validate the SWAT+ outputs on water balance elements using the results of the field-scale model; ii) to produce reference data for calibrating the water balance elements simulated by SWAT+ at field level and iii) to find the best approach for implementing management measures in the models.

The field-scale modelling is performed at seven selected sites, representing the boreal, continental, and Pannonian biogeographical regions of Europe. At all stages within the field-scale modelling, we strive to follow the “good modelling practice” principles (van Waveren et al., 2000), including model selection, set up, calibration, validation, and evaluation of the results. The SWAP version 4 documentation (Kroes et al., 2017) covers the theoretical background of the SWAP model in detail including model input and output files.

This protocol gives an overview of the main steps of the modelling procedure and serves as a handbook and guideline for field-scale modellers within the OPTAIN project.

2. Field-scale models in the OPTAIN project

In the OPTAIN project, we aim to evaluate the effects of NSWORMs on hydrological processes at both field and catchment scales. The smallest spatial unit parameterised and evaluated in the SWAT+ catchment-scale model is the field. Compared to SWAT (model version 2012), the SWAT+ model incorporates several innovative elements to better account for connectivity and small-scale processes within the watershed. The description of small-scale processes, as soil hydrological regime, however, is still partly based on semi-empirical elements in SWAT+.

Within the OPTAIN project, we use a multi-scale modelling approach by linking a profile/plot scale soil hydrological model to SWAT+. Process-based soil hydrological models incorporate exact description of water transport within the soil profile and, therefore, can be used for validating the SWAT+ results for the selected sites and for fine-tuning the (semi-)empirical parameters of the SWAT+ model.

The field-scale modelling is performed at seven selected sites, representing the boreal (Dotnuvele and Kråkstadselva), continental (Černiči, Petite Glane and Upper Zgłowiaczka) and Pannonian (Csorsza and Tetves) biogeographical regions, as demonstrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Locations of the seven pilot sites involved in field-scale modelling in OPTAIN

2.1. Catchment- and field-scale hydrological models

Hydrologists and soil scientists generally understand different types of models when referring to “hydrological models”. A study from Devi et al. (2015) titled “A Review of Hydrological Models” concerned catchment-scale models such as SWAT, MIKE-SHE, HBV, TOPMODEL and VIC, yet did not mention the rather large family of profile- and field-scale hydrological models. Horton et al. (2021) reviewed 157 scientific papers about 22 hydrological models, all of which used for simulating runoff and/or water quality at the catchment scale. On the other hand, Tenreiro et al. (2020) compared seven “crop simulation models” and five “hydrological models”, using the latter expression for both, profile- or field-scale soil hydrological models like HYDRUS and SWAP as well as for the watershed model SWIM.

Catchment- and field-scale hydrological models, however, differ conceptually, as they focus on different processes and are applied for different purposes. An evaluation of different hydrological models at the spatio-temporal scale (Figure 2) shows that the finer the spatial and temporal scales are, the more process-based elements can be built in a model.

Figure 2. Different hydrological models in their respective spatio-temporal scales

Models handling larger scales in time and space contain more empirical elements, as it becomes difficult to account for the spatial variability of different properties, e.g., of crops, soils in a case study. Consequently, while catchment-level hydrogeochemical models like SWAT, INCA etc. simulate the reaction of a whole watershed, its sub-catchments or of hydrotopes focusing mostly on simulating discharge and instream water quality.

However, when it comes to the dynamics and redistribution of water within the soil profile itself, such as soil water balance and root water uptake, it is believed that soil hydrological models (SWAP, HYDRUS, etc.) are more capable. These models can give more precise estimates of soil water content and crop transpiration. They can describe changes in soil properties due to soil tillage, land use, and other factors in a more sophisticated way. Table 1 provides an overview on the processes described in different hydrological models.

Table 1. Processes in focus in different catchment-scale (SWAT+ , INCA) and field-scale (DrainMod, COUP, SWAP) hydrological models.

Model layer	Processes	Hydrological models						
		Soil hydrological models			Catchment-scale models			
		DrainMod	COUP	SWAP	SWAT+	INCA		
Above ground vegetation zone	Precipitation	Driving	Driving	Driving	Driving	Driving		
	Snow dynamics							
	Interception							
	Transpiration							
Soil surface	Evaporation							
	Surface runoff							
	Infiltration							
	Unsaturated zone	Macropore flow						
		Plant water uptake						
		Soil water redistribution						
		Capillary rise						
		Water flow in frozen soil						
		Lateral flow to stream						
		Subsurface drainage flow						
		Percolation to sat. zone						
		Saturated zone	Lateral inflow	as input	as input	as input		
			Capillary rise to unsat. zone					
			Recharge to deep aquifer					
			Base flow					
CONFINING LAYER								
DEEP AQUIFER								

- process-based calculation with parameters that have physical meaning
- calculated using semi-empirical methods
- calculated using empirical methods
- can be implemented indirectly by an experienced model user
- the model can not account for this process
- implemented through input data from other sources

2.2. Field-scale model selection

In OPTAIN, we follow the recommendations of van Waveren et al. (2020). Concerning model selection, they suggest accounting for several factors when choosing the actual simulation model(s) or model package(s). The outcome of a particular modelling study strongly depends on – besides the model itself – i) the quality, resolution, and amount of the input data available and used; ii) the quality and extent of the expert knowledge about locally prevailing conditions; and iii) the validity of any assumptions that are inevitably made while parameterizing the model (Van Waveren et al., 2000; Farkas and Hagyó, 2010; Deelstra et al., 2010). Therefore, it is important to test the model's suitability for the study area and to find the balance between both the model's spatial and temporal resolution vs. the resolution and availability of the data, model simplicity and ease of use given the experts' familiarity with the simulation model(s).

Saloranta et al. (2003) established a set of operational and functional selection criteria for mathematical models designed for simulating hydrological and biogeochemical processes in the terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. These criteria, the so-called "benchmark-criteria" can also guide potential model users in selecting the appropriate model for use in other areas as well. The benchmark criteria are presented in the form of 14 questions with a 3-tier response system through which each model can be evaluated. The three tiers are "Relevance", "Sensitivity" and "Ease-of-use". Based on the benchmark criteria, a preliminary model evaluation can be performed to select an appropriate mathematical model which meets the goals of the study. The list of criteria that was deemed most important is as follows:

- Q1.1. How well does the model's output relate to the management task?
- Q1.2. How well does the model's resolution match the requirements of the task?
- Q1.3. How well has the model been tested?
- Q1.4. How complicated is the model in relation to the task?
- Q1.5. How is the balance between the models' input data and data availability?
- Q1.8. How is the peer acceptance for the model with scientific theory?
- Q3.5. How is the model's flexibility for adaptation and improvements

In OPTAIN, we developed a model evaluation workbook, listing this set of questions with detailed explanations for supporting the model selection exercise. The worksheets, used for evaluating different models are given in Appendices 1-3. The scores are automatically summed up. The final score accounts for the modelling experience of the evaluator with respect to each model (Appendix 4).

The model selection procedure was performed in an early stage of the project. Using the above-described benchmark criteria based method, the SWAP model was selected as the common field-scale model in the OPTAIN project. Therefore, this modelling protocol was written for the SWAP model, focusing on Version 4.0.1.

3. Input data

The modelling procedure for the SWAP model is presented in Figure 3. In this chapter we describe the input data and their possible sources.

Figure 3. Overview of the modelling procedure when using the SWAP field-scale model and the data required for running and calibrating the model (the figure is after Feddes, 2007)

Possible sources of input data for field-scale models are given in the relevant sub-chapters.

3.1. The SWAP v4.0.1. input files

The basic set up of the SWAP model consists of three file types: the main SWAP file, the weather data file, and the crop file. Several optional file types can be defined as given in Table 2.

Table 2. Input data files to be defined for the SWAP v4.0.1. model

Description	Extension	Status	Defined	Comment
Main SWAP file	*.swp	required	command line	Described in (sub)chapter
			SECTIONS	General section 4.1
				Meteorology section 3.2 and 4.2
				Crop section 3.4 and 4.3
				Soil water section 3.3 and 4.4
				Lateral drainage section 3.5
				Bottom boundary section 3.6.2
				Heat flow section 4.5
			Solute transport section not used at this stage	
Meteorological input file	*.yyy	required	in *.swp file	one file per year; defined by METFIL
Crop input file	*.crp	required	in *.swp file	one file per crop; defined by CROPFIL
Lateral drainage input data	*.dra	optional	in *.swp file	if SWDRA = 2, file name defined by DRFIL
Detailed rainfall records	*.yyy	optional	in *.swp file	if SWRAIN = 3, file name defined by RAINFIL
Irrigation data	*.irg	optional	in *.swp file	if SWIRGFIL = 1, file name defined by IRGFIL
Runon data	*.inc	optional	in *.swp file	if SWRUNON = 1, file name defined by RUFIL
User-defined soil input data	*.csv	optional	in *.swp file	if SWSOPHY = 1, file name defined by FILENAMESOPHY
Bottom boundary conditions	*.bbc	optional	in *.swp file	if SWBBCFILE = 1, file name defined by BBCFIL
Top boundary condition - soil temperature	*.tss	optional	in *.swp file	if SwTopbHea = 1, defined by TSOILFILE

3.2. Meteorological data

Proper and reliable weather information is essential for accurate water regime modelling, as meteorological input data are the main driving variables for hydrological models at any scales. The most important data are precipitation and air temperature. Precipitation determines the main input of water in the system. Air temperature and other weather factors determine the upper boundary conditions at the soil surface.

3.2.1. Type of weather data required by the SWAP model

The SWAP model requires daily or sub-daily meteorological data, measured within or in the pilot field. These data serve as driving variables for running the model. There are obligatory data, and some optional ones, which should be given in units as listed in Table 3.

Table 3. Meteorological input data requirement of the SWAP model

DATA	Description	Unit	Status
Tmin	minimum air temperature	°C	required
Tmax	maximum air temperature	°C	required
RAD	solar radiation	kJ m^{-2}	required
HUM	vapour pressure	kPa	required
WIND	wind speed	m s^{-1}	required
RAIN	precipitation	mm	required
Etref	potential evapotranspiration	mm	optional
WET	fraction of day with precipitation	day	optional

The SWAP model requires meteorological data in a specific format. The required format for daily weather data is shown in Figure 4. The data is stored in one text file per station per year, with a file extension equivalent to the last three digits of the respective year (i.e., "Meteofile.003" for year 2003). The format of the model input data is restricted and differs depending on whether the data is given in daily or sub-daily resolution (Figures 4 and 5 respectively). Temporal resolution of weather data is defined by the switch SWMETDETAIL in the main SWAP file *.swp, indicating daily or sub-daily time intervals with a value of 0 or 1, respectively. Missing values are marked as -99.0.

```

*****
*      Filename:      Fonyód 2014
*      Contents:      SWAP- 4- Daily meteorological data
*****
*      Comment       area: Pannonia, Tetves watershed, arable land
*      Field-scale modelling, OPTAIN project,
*
*****
Station  DD      MM      YYYY      RAD      Tmin      Tmax      HUM      WIND      RAIN      ETref      WET
*        nr      nr      nr      kJ/m2     oC      oC      kPa      m/s      mm      mm      d
*****
'Fonyod'  1        1        2014      1643.5    2.7      4.4      0.74     3.0      0.0 -99.0 -99.0
'Fonyod'  2        1        2014      4448.1    2.7      8.4      0.74     3.0      0.0 -99.0 -99.0
'Fonyod'  3        1        2014      5789.3    0.7      11.4     0.64     3.0      0.0 -99.0 -99.0
'Fonyod'  4        1        2014      1839.3    1.7      4.4      0.69     3.0      0.1 -99.0 -99.0
'Fonyod'  5        1        2014      2881.9    3.7      8.4      0.80     3.0      0.1 -99.0 -99.0

```

Figure 4. SWAP meteorological input data in daily resolution

Unlike the SWAT and SWAT+ models, the SWAP model does not use a weather generator, therefore missing data are not allowed for required meteorological variables. It is recommended to estimate the missing values before completing the meteorological input files for the SWAP model.

The potential evapotranspiration (ET_{ref}) can be given as an input variable. If such data are missing (which is indicated by -99.0 values), the model calculates the ET values using the Penman-Monteith equation (Penman, 1948; Monteith, 1965). The SWETR switch in the main SWAP file (*.swp) indicates the use of measured (SWETR=1) or calculated by the model (SWETR=0) potential evapotranspiration values.

```
* Source of data      : Lithuanian Hydrometeorological Service
* File content       : Meteo data for Doutnuvele station, Boreal area, OPTAIN project)
* File generated at  : 2021-02-24 08:14:12
Date,Record,Rad,Temp,Hum,Wind,Rain
2021-01-02,1,0.0,-2.0,0.530,1.0,0.0
2021-01-02,2,0.0,-2.3,0.520,0.9,0.0
2021-01-02,3,0.0,-2.5,0.500,1.0,0.0
2021-01-02,4,0.0,-2.9,0.490,0.2,0.0
```

Figure 5. SWAP meteorological input data in sub-daily resolution

Sub-daily (most commonly hourly) resolution of meteorological variables can be important for capturing the rapid water transport processes during heavy rainfall events. For such input files the hourly average air temperature is given (instead of the daily minimum and maximum values) (Figure 5). The units are the same as listed in Table 2. It is important to mention, that the SWAP 4.x manual (Kores et al., 2017) shows another structure for sub-daily weather data, but the SWAP 4.0.1. executable provided is running with the weather input files from older version, which are structured as presented in Figure 5.

For advanced users there are more options to account for rainfall intensity even when the other weather data are given in daily resolution, using the switch SWRAIN:

```
SWRAIN = 0 ! Switch for use of actual rainfall intensity (only if SWMETDETAIL = 0):
           ! 0 = Use daily rainfall amounts (case of Figure 4)
           ! 1 = Use daily rainfall amounts + mean intensity
           ! 2 = Use daily rainfall amounts + duration (case of Figure 5)
           ! 3 = Use detailed rainfall records (dt < 1 day), as supplied in separate file
```

If SWRAIN=1, the user should provide a table directly in the *.swp file indicating the day of the year (TIME) and the rainfall intensity (RAINFLUX) in mm per day:

```
* If SWRAIN = 1, specify mean rainfall intensity RAINFLUX [0.d0..1000.d0 mm/d, R]
* as function of Julian time TIME [0..366 d, R], maximum 30 records
TIME  RAINFLUX
1.0   20.0
360.0 20.0
* End of table
```

If SWRAIN=3, a separate file should be given with detailed rainfall data.

3.2.2. Tools developed for creating SWAP weather data input files

As the specific format of the meteorological input data for SWAP is time-consuming and error-prone to be created manually, a script was created to automate the process. An easy-to-use Excel template is used as input data for that script (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Excel template for creating meteorological input data for the SWAP model in daily resolution

An automation of this process enables quick transformation of case-study specific weather data into SWAP readable format. Additionally, this allows for the possibility of running SWAP under multi-model ensemble modelling for the future climate for each case study, as this process would potentially require thousands of SWAP meteorological input files, which would otherwise be too time intensive to be created by hand. (See also OPTAIN Deliverable 3.3: “Created data pre-processors successfully applied for input data restructuring” (Čerkasova et al., 2022)).

Once the Excel template sheet has been filled out with desired data, the script can be run. The script prompts the user to select the location of the template sheet using a GUI file explorer, followed by the desired location of the output files. After these two steps have been taken, the script generates the SWAP compatible output files to the desired location. The R-script is documented, and the Excel template sheet provides notes to describe its function. Additionally, a more detailed readme file is available providing step-by-step instructions. The manual hard calibration tool consists of the R-script, a template, a readme file, and an example output file, which are available for the OPTAIN field-scale modellers. The tool will be publicly available after careful testing and verification.

3.3. Soil data

Soil properties are the most complex and influential properties in soil hydrological modelling. Soil properties determine water retention within the landscape and can be modified with various tillage systems and cropping practices. Thus, knowledge of soil properties and their sensitivity to various practices is essential for evaluating the efficiency of the water retention measures. Considerable spatial variability in soil hydraulic properties exists in nature, even if these are considered homogenous by most of the soil hydrological models (Tenreiro et al., 2020). Moreover, surface soil structure is sensitive to natural and anthropogenic impacts resulting in temporal variability of soil hydraulic properties (Farkas et al., 2006). Nevertheless, most hydrological modelling studies consider soil hydraulic properties as temporally constant when predicting the flow of water and solutes in the atmosphere-plant-soil system. Chandrasekhar et al. (2018) introduced a simple approach of accounting for temporal changes in soil hydraulic properties in modelling the soil water regime. They concluded that the limiting factor to efficiently calibrate and apply such modelling tools is not in the theoretical part, but rather the lack of adequate soil structural and hydrologic data.

As described above, there are many issues with soil hydraulic properties in hydrological modelling, but the biggest issue is the lack of appropriate data. That is why we consider the soil hydraulic properties as a calibration parameter, aiming to come up with values that are representative for the selected case in the spatio-temporal context of the given study. The outcome, however, strongly depends on how precisely we can identify soil properties in the initial model setup. In the followings, we describe the type of soil data needed to run the SWAP model and the possible data sources.

3.3.1. Discretization of the soil profile

Discretization of the soil profile in a SWAP project is an important step. It determines i) how precisely a natural soil body is represented in the model and ii) the accuracy of the simulations defined by the numerical structure. A scheme on the discretization of soil profiles in SWAP is presented in Figure 7. The genetic soil layers (ISOILLAY) and their thickness should be identified first; the A1, A2, B and C soil layers of a 48 cm deep soil profile have a thickness of 2, 8, 20 and 18 cm in the example, respectively. Each soil layer can further be divided into sub-layers (ISUBLAY). Data on vertical discretization of the soil profile contains the height of each sublayer (HSUBLAY) and their discretization – a certain number (NCOMP) of identically thick layers (HCOMP) within the same sublayer, for which the model will calculate the soil water regime and the water balance elements separately. Those are the basic calculation units.

Figure 7. Example of vertical discretization of a soil profile in accordance with SWAP input requirements

The numerical discretization of the soil profile shown in Figure 7 can be defined in part 4 of the soil water section of the *.swp file:

```

* Part 4: Vertical discretization of soil profile
* Specify the following data (maximum MACP lines):
* ISUBLAY = number of sub layer, start with 1 at soil surface [1..MACP, I]
* ISOILLAY = number of soil physical layer, start with 1 at soil surface [1..MAHO, I]
* HSUBLAY = height of sub layer [0..1.d4 cm, R]
* HCOMP = height of compartments in the sub layer [0..1000.0 cm, R]
* NCOMP = number of compartments in the sub layer (Mind NCOMP=HSUBLAY/HCOMP) [1..MACP, I]

ISOILLAY  ISUBLAY  HSUBLAY  HCOMP  NCOMP
1          1        2.0      2.0     1
2          2        4.0      4.0     1
3          2        4.0      4.0     1
4          3       10.0     5.0     2
5          3       10.0     5.0     2
6          4        8.0      8.0     1
* end of table

```

Thus, NCOMP shows how many HCOMPs of similar thicknesses are located within the same HSUBLAY. It is important to fulfil the conditions of $NCOMP * HCOMP = HSUBLAY$.

3.3.2. Soil hydraulic functions

The basic soil properties used by the SWAP model are the soil hydraulic functions, defined for each ISOILLAY. These are the soil water retention curve and the hydraulic conductivity functions, both needed to solve the basic equation of water flow in a porous media – the Richard’s equation (Kroes et al. 2017).

The soil water retention curve shows the relationship between the soil water content (θ) and soil water potential, or pressure head (h), as presented in Figure 8. In the SWAP parameters, θ is represented with the character “O”.

Figure 8. Soil water retention curves ($\theta=f(h)$) for two different soils.

Due to the wide pressure ranges returned from very wet to very dry conditions, water potential is normally expressed in logarithmic form: pF (log₁₀ of the pressure expressed in hPa). The soil water content at saturation (OSAT; $h=0$) reflects the total porosity of the soil and depends on soil structure, texture (mechanical composition), and bulk density. The field capacity (FC) and the wilting point (WP) reflect the soil water content at water potentials of 2.3 and 4.2 (lg(cm)), respectively. The residual water content, ORES is defined as the soil water content for which the gradient $d\theta/dh$ becomes 0. In other words, it corresponds to chemically bounded water remaining in the soil at very high pF values that cannot be extracted from the soil under natural conditions. ORES is determined by soil texture and organic matter content.

NPAR and ALFA are empirical fitting parameters, determining the shape of the soil water retention curve. ALFA corresponds, approximately to the inverse of the air-entry value, whilst NPAR is a shape-defining parameter (Guber and Pachepsky, 2010).

Figure 9 demonstrates the shape of the hydraulic conductivity function (K-function), which expresses the drop in soil water conductivity as the soil dries out.

As the numerical solution of the Richard's equation requires continuous functions, soil hydraulic models use different analytical relationships for describing the soil hydraulic functions. The most used expression is the so-called van Genuchten-Mualem (VGM) model (van Genuchten, 1980). Therefore, the basic soil input data required by the SWAP model are the parameters of the VGM function.

Figure 9. Soil hydraulic conductivity functions for two different soils

Soil hydraulic input data needs to be provided in part 5 of the soil water section of the *.swp file, as follows:

* Part 5: Soil hydraulic functions
 * Switch for analytical functions or tabular input:
 SWSOPHY = 0 ! 0 = Analytical functions with input of Mualem - van Genuchten parameters
 ! 1 = Soil physical tables
 * **If SWSOPHY = 0, specify MvG parameters** for each soil physical layer (max. MAHO):
 * ISOILLAY1 = number of soil physical layer, as defined in part 4 [1..MAHO, I]
 * ORES = Residual water content [0..1 cm³/cm³, R]
 * OSAT = Saturated water content [0..1 cm³/cm³, R]
 * ALFA = Parameter alpha of main drying curve [0.0001..100 /cm, R]
 * NPAR = Parameter n [1.001..9 -, R]
 * KSATFIT = Fitting parameter Ksat of hydraulic conductivity function [1.d-5..1d5 cm/d, R]
 * LEXP = Exponent in hydraulic conductivity function [-25..25 -, R]
 * ALFAW = Alfa parameter of main wetting curve in case of hysteresis [0.0001..100 /cm, R]
 * H_ENPR = Air entry pressure head [-40.0..0.0 cm, R]
 * KSATEXM = Measured hydraulic conductivity at saturated conditions [1.d-5..1d5 cm/d, R]
 * BDENS = Dry soil bulk density [100..1d4 mg/cm³, R]

ISOILLAY1	ORES	OSAT	ALFA	NPAR	KSATFIT	LEXP	ALFAW	H_ENPR	KSATEXM	BDENS	
1	0.01	0.42	0.028	1.491	12.52	-	1.060	0.0542	0.0	12.52	1315.0
2	0.02	0.38	0.0213	1.951	12.68	0.168	0.0426	0.0	12.68	1315.0	

* --- end of table

SWAP soil input parameters ORES, OSAT, ALFA, NPAR, KSATFIT and LEXP are the parameters of the VGM function, corresponding to *drying initial conditions* (see details in sub-chapter 4.4, Part 6). They can be either fitted to measured points of the soil water retention curve and K-function, or estimated using so-called pedotransfer functions (PTFs), see sub-chapter 3.3.3.

The ALFAW is used for calculating hysteresis (sub-chapter 4.4., Part 6); there is limited data on hysteresis in the literature, therefore this function is optional. If ALFAW = ALFA, no hysteresis is considered.

If there is measured data on saturated hydraulic conductivity, the KSATEXM parameter can be used. KSATEXM accounts for water transport via soil matrix and macropores, therefore it is always higher than KSATFIT, which represents the soil matrix. The bulk density can be either measured or estimated, using PTFs.

3.3.3. Identifying the soil hydraulic functions

As mentioned in sub-chapter 3.2.2, soil hydraulic functions can either be fitted to measured soil hydraulic data or estimated by using pedotransfer functions.

Analytical functions of soil hydraulic properties can be fitted to measured water retention and/or hydraulic conductivity data, using the RETention Curve (RETC) tool (van Genuchten et al., 1991). The tool is available on PC-Progress website [Link to RETC tool](#). RETC can fit different analytical models to the measured data (Fig. 10).

Figure 10. Types of analytical models available in the RETC tool

For the basic SWAP parameters, the van Genuchten model, assuming $m = 1 - 1/n$, should be chosen. The output can be directly transferred into part 5 of the soil water part of the *.swp file.

In some cases, however, the “simple” van Genuchten function does not properly describe the shape of the measured soil hydraulic data, so other analytical models should be tested. The parameters of those models cannot be directly incorporated in the SWAP model. In such cases, user-defined soil parameters should be used. The SWSOPHY key is the one to use when choosing between VGM parameters (SWSOPHY =0) or user-defined soil hydraulic tables:

* If **SWSOPHY = 1**, specify names of input files [A80] with soil hydraulic tables for each soil layer:
 FILENAMESOPHY = 'topsoil_sand_B2.csv', 'subsoil_sand_O2.csv'

The structure of the user-defined soil input files is given in Figure 11 (right). When the RETC program is used for fitting various analytical functions to measured soil properties, the requested h , θ and K data can be directly taken from the RETC output file. Soil input files should be created separately for each ISOILLAY.

If no measured soil hydraulic data are available, estimation functions – PTFs – should be used to estimate the soil hydraulic functions from other, easier available soil properties. There are several options to find appropriate PTFs, some of them are described in chapter 3.4 of the OPTAIN SWAT+ modelling protocol (Annex 1).

When limited soil data is available, a simple and quick approach is to use the ROSETTA neural network, incorporated in the RETC software, for estimating the VGM parameters from various soil properties. The ROSETTA computer program is described by Schaap et al. (2001).

	h	θ	K
1	headtab	thetatab	conductab
2	-1E+07	0.103427	3.90E-13
3	-5000000	0.109281	1.64E-12
4	-2000000	0.118016	1.10E-11
5	-1500000	0.121015	2.00E-11
6	-1200000	0.123432	3.18E-11
7	-1000000	0.125468	4.64E-11
8	-500000	0.133737	1.95E-10
9	-200000	0.146074	1.31E-09
10	-150000	0.150311	2.38E-09
11	-120000	0.153725	3.78E-09
12	-100000	0.156601	5.51E-09

- h – water potential (cm)
- Q – soil water content ($\text{cm}^3 \text{cm}^{-3}$)
- K – hydraulic conductivity (cm day^{-1})
- Use small increments
- Separate file for each layer

Figure 11. Table format for user-defined soil data

For applying ROSETTA, the “neural network prediction” bottom should be selected in the “Water flow parameters” window of RETC. This opens the inbuilt ROSETTA platform, where several options can be chosen, depending on data availability (Figure 12). The disadvantage of this estimation method is that it was developed using soil data mainly from the US, so the uncertainty of the predicted parameters is rather high. Therefore, it is always recommended to use pedotransfer functions, developed for the study site or region, if such are available.

Figure 12. Using the ROSETTA neural network for estimating the VGM parameters

3.4. Agricultural management

Agricultural management and plant growth play an important role in SWAP, and in the SWAT+ model setup. Within the OPTAIN project, some of the NSWORMs are related to management practices, including soil tillage, crop rotations, introduction of winter crops, interrow crops, or new crops in line with climate change. Thus, proper definition of crop rotation and plant parameters is important i) for precise water balance calculations with respect to validation of the SWAT+ model outputs against SWAP model results, and ii) for improved understanding of the effects of management measures on water regime and related processes.

The crop section defines the crop rotation scheme for the modelled period and the name of the crop files with plant data. The plant data are given in a separate file.

3.4.1. Crop rotation scheme

The crop rotation scheme is given in part 1 of the crop section of the *.swp file. The switch between bare or cultivated soil (SWCROP) should be set first. For cultivated soils, information about crop type and crop rotation should be given:

```
* Part 1: Crop rotation scheme

* Switch for bare soil or cultivated soil
SWCROP = 1! 0 = Bare soil ! 1 = Cultivated soil

* Specify for each crop (maximum MACROP):
* INITCRP = type of initialisation of crop growth: emergence (default) = 1, sowing = 2 [-]
* CROPSTART = date of crop emergence [dd-mmm-yyyy]
* CROPEND = date of crop harvest [dd-mmm-yyyy]
* CROPNAME = crop name [A40]
* CROPFIL = name of file with crop input parameters without extension. CRP, [A40]
* CROPTYPE = growth module:
* 1 = simple; 2 = detailed, WOFOST general; 3 = detailed, WOFOST grass
```

INITCRP	CROPSTART	CROPEND	CROPNAME	CROPFIL	CROPTYPE
1	01-may-2016	15-oct-2016	'Maize'	'MaizeS_4'	1
2	30-sep-2016	06-aug-2017	'Winter wheat'	'WintCer2'	1
2	31-aug-2017	04-apr-2018	'Cereal+grass'	'GrassS'	1
1	20-apr-2018	15-aug-2018	'Maize'	'MaizeS_4'	1
1	02-sep-2018	15-nov-2018	'Mustard'	'GrassS'	1
1	22-mar-2019	15-jul-2019	'Pea'	'PeaS_4'	1
1	25-sep-2019	14-aug-2020	'Winter wheat'	'WinterCer2'	1
1	14-aug-2020	05-sep-2020	'Winter barley'	'WinterCer1'	1
1	25-jul-2021	31-dec-2021	'Oil seed rape'	'Rape'	1

```
* End of table
```

SWAP can calculate crop growth starting at both, sowing date (INITCROP=2) or date of emergence (INITCROP=1). This can be overwritten in the crop file (*.crp) for each crop, using the IDEV parameter. If IDEV equals one, the length of crop cycle is fixed and the dates, indicated in the crop rotation scheme of the *.swp file using CROPSTART and CROPEND are used. Setting IDEV to two, the phenology will be driven by the temperature sums.

The CROPNAME is defined by the user and informs about the real crop grown in the area. If the crop file for that crop type is missing parameters for another, similar crop are used for the calculations. The CROPFIL and CROPTYPE parameters are important. SWAP will look for crop files for each particular year named as initiated in CROPFIL and with an extension *.crp. Thus, for the case demonstrated above there must be six crop files in the folder, defined in *.swp by PATHCRP: MaizeS_4.crp, WinterCer2.crp; GrassS.crp; PeaS_4.crp; WinterCer1.crp and Rape.crp.

As mentioned above, bare soil can be represented setting the switch SWCROP to zero. This, however, means that there is no crop on the soil surface existing for the whole modelled period. If the soil is left bare for a particle year, a BareSoil.crp crop file could be used and included in the crop rotation scheme:

* CROPTYPE = growth module: 1 = simple; 2 = detailed, WOFOST general; 3 = detailed, WOFOST grass

INITCRP	CROPSTART	CROPEND	CROPNAME	CROPFIL	CROPTYPE
1	01-jan-2018	20-aug-2018	'WintCer1'	'WintCer1'	1
1	01-oct-2019	26-jul-2020	'WintCer2'	'WintCer2'	1
1	01-jan-2021	01-may-2022	'no crop'	'BareSoil'	1
1	02-may-2022	10-oct-2022	'Maize'	Maize'	1

* End of table

3.4.2. Crop data

Crop data are given in a separate *.crp file. SWAP can use a simple and a complex crop routine to simulate crop water demand and crop yield. The complex crop routine is that of the World Food Studies (WOFOST) model, which is very parameter-demanding. However, this is the only option for calculating crop yields. The simple crop routine also uses a lot of parameters and is designed for calculating the water demand of the crop precisely. As the WOFOST parameters are very complex and hard to gain, we use the simple crop routine in OPTAIN considering the plant water uptake as a crop yield indicator.

An example SWAP crop input file for running the simple crop routine is given in Appendix 5. Some of the crop parameters listed in parts 3-6 of the *.crp file can be measured, and if such site-specific measurements exist, it is recommended to use those in the initial model setup. These data are the leaf area index (LAI), soil cover fraction (SCF), crop height (CH) and rooting depth (RD) as a function of the development stage (DVS). All the crop parameters and the phases of the DVS are provided in the SWAP manual (Kroes et al., 2017).

Parameters governing the soil water extraction by plant roots are listed in part 7 of the *.crp file, indicating water stress due to both, extremely high and low soil water content. Salinity stress parameters can be defined in part 8. Interception can be set for both, closed forests or agricultural crops in part 9.

3.4.3. Crop database

Within the OPTAIN project, a SWAP crop database is being developed. The database contains all the static and dynamic (DVS-dependent) parameters of the *.crp files of the SWAP simple crop routine and contains data for various plants, including forests, grasslands, and agricultural crops. The crop database is stored in an Excel format and available for the OPTAIN consortium partners. In the same folder, SWAP crop files for simple and detailed crop routines can be found and downloaded from the relevant subfolders for direct use. Please note, that many of the example crop files, given with the SWAP 4.0.1 model version are only valid for older versions of the SWAP model, and will give error messages. The OPTAIN field-scale modelling team upgraded those example files to SWAP version 4.x. So, we recommend using the *.crp files, available on the UFZ GIT instead of those, currently provided by the model developers.

3.4.4. Irrigation

The SWAP model can handle both, fixed irrigation with known dates and amounts, and optimising irrigation according to given criteria. In the OPTAIN project, the irrigation

amounts are mostly known. In this case, “fixed irrigation application” must be chosen in part 2 of the *.swp file (switch SWIRFIX = 1), and the irrigation data can be given in table format (SWIRGFIL=0) or as a separate file (SWIRGFIL=1):

```
* Part 2: Fixed irrigation applications

* Switch for fixed irrigation applications
SWIRFIX = 1 ! 0 = no irrigation applications are prescribed
           ! 1 = irrigation applications are prescribed

* If SWIRFIX = 1, specify:

* Switch for separate file with irrigation data
SWIRGFIL = 0 ! 0 = irrigation data are specified below
           ! 1 = irrigation data are specified in a separate file

* If SWIRGFIL = 0 specify the following information of each fixed irrigation event (max. MAIRG):
* IRDATE = date of irrigation [dd-mmm-yyyy]
* IRDEPTH = amount of water during the day [0..1000 mm, R]
* IRCONC = salt concentration of irrigation water [0..1000 mg/cm3, R]
* IRTYPE = type of irrigation: sprinkling = 0, surface = 1

  IRDATE IRDEPTH IRCONC IRTYPE
  05-jan-2013  15.0  0.45  1
  22-jun-2013  10.0  0.96  1
* end of table

* If SWIRGFIL = 1, specify name of file with irrigation data:
IRGFIL = 'testirri' ! File name without extension .IRG [A32]
```

Where MAIRG stands for the maximum number of applied irrigations. The default, inbuilt array length is 10000. The array length can be redefined by adjusting the value of the MAIRG parameter in the param.fi file and recompilation of the FORTRAN code of the SWAP model. “R” refers to real values in free format. Thus, the data should not be an integer, but expressed in decimals.

For both, table format or separate file, the date, depth, type (sprinkling or surface irrigation) and the concentration of the irrigation water should be given.

The SWAP crop file (*.crp) contains further, more sophisticated approaches for irrigation scheduling (Appendix 5). This option can be activated, setting the switch SCHEDULE to 1. Further, the user can choose from the combination of five different timing options for irrigation, values 0 and 1 standing for inactive, or active conditions, respectively:

1. Daily stress (TSC1, 1 or 0)
2. Depletion of readily available water (TSC2, 1 or 0)
3. Depletion of totally available water (TSC3, 1 or 0)
4. Depletion water amount (TSC4, 1 or 0)
5. Pressure head or moisture content (TSC5, 1 or 0)

The irrigation depth can be fixed (DSC2=1) or calculated so that the water content of the soil profile would return to field capacity level (DSC1=1).

Using the irrigation scheduling scheme, appropriate and water-saving irrigation strategies can be tested or set up in time.

3.5. Drainage data

3.5.1. The lateral drainage section of the main SWAP file *.swp

Subsurface drainage is important in areas, where the soil is too wet during spring and becomes trafficable rather late, causing delays in sowing, and in areas with naturally high groundwater table. In the OPTAIN project, the first case concerns the Norwegian, the second the Czech case study.

Drainage modifies the soil water balance elements and influences the transport of water at field, and even at catchment scale. By accelerating the transport of water from the root zone to the catchment outlet, drainage can contribute to increase in soil and nutrient losses.

The OPTAIN project aims at optimising the various management practices and measures from different aspects, including hydrological and water quality issues. Since subsurface drainage can have contradictory effects - favourable for water regime but not for surface water quality, it is important to correctly describe subsurface drainage processes and how these processes are influenced by management measures under present and future climate conditions.

The drainage section of the SWAP model is rather complex. The type of drainage system is defined in the lateral drainage section of the *.swp file:

```

*** LATERAL DRAINAGE SECTION ***
* Specify whether lateral drainage to surface water should be included

SWDRA = 0 ! Switch, simulation of lateral drainage:
! 0 = No simulation of drainage
! 1 = Simulation with basic drainage routine
! 2 = Simulation of drainage with surface water management

* If SWDRA = 1 or SWDRA = 2 specify name of file with drainage input data:
DRFIL = 'SB' ! File name with drainage input data without extension .DRA [A16]

```

The main sections and sub-sections in the SWAP drainage file (*.dra) are listed below:

- I. Basic drainage section (SWDRA=1)
 - a. Table with drainage flux as function of groundwater level (DRAMET=1)
 - b. Drainage formula of “Hooghoudt or Ernst” (DRAMET=2)
 - c. Drainage and/or infiltration resistance, multi-level if needed (DRAMET=3)
- II. Extended drainage section (SWDRA=2)

In the SWAP drainage file, there are options for single and multiple drainage levels, the latter being characteristic e.g., for the Netherlands. Our case studies have at most one drainage level.

After reading the relevant sections in the SWAP manual and having discussions with the local experts, we decided to use the drainage formula of Hooghoudt or Ernst for calculating lateral drainage.

Option I/a was not possible, as no measured data is available to provide values in table format. Option I/c is recommended for multi-level drainage systems. Option II assumes drainage with surface water management, which is not the case for the OPTAIN pilot fields.

3.5.2. The SWAP drainage file, *.dra

The main setup of the drainage system as well as the drainage features are defined in the *.dra input file. The full structure of the *.dra file can be overlooked in the OPTAIN example SWAP projects with drainage ([SWAP example project, LT, available for the OPTAIN consortium partners](#)) or in Chapter 4.5 of the SWAP protocol (Kroes et al., 2017).

The structure and the parameters of the *.dra file for the I/b case is given below.

* Part 2: Drainage formula of Hooghoudt or Ernst (DRAMET = 2)

```
* Drain characteristics:
LM2 = 11.    ! Drain spacing [1..1000 m, R]
SHAPE = 0.8  ! Shape factor to account for actual location between drain and water divide [0.0..1.0 -, R]
WETPER = 30.0 ! Wet perimeter of the drain [0..1000 cm, R]
ZBOTDR = -80.0 ! Level of drain bottom [-1000..0 cm, R, negative below soil surface]
ENTRES = 20.0 ! Drain entry resistance [0..1000 d, R]

* Soil profile characteristics:
IPOS = 2     ! Switch for position of drain:
              ! 1 = On top of an impervious layer in a homogeneous profile
              ! 2 = Above an impervious layer in a homogeneous profile
              ! 3 = At the interface of a fine upper and a coarse lower soil layer
              ! 4 = In the lower, more coarse soil layer
              ! 5 = In the upper, more fine soil layer

* For all positions specify:
BASEGW = -200. ! Level of impervious layer [-1d4..0 cm, R]
KHTOP = 25.    ! Horizontal hydraulic conductivity top layer [0..1000 cm/d, R]

* In case IPOS = 3,4, or 5, specify also
KHBOT = 10.0  ! Horizontal hydraulic conductivity bottom layer [0..1000 cm/d, R]
ZINTF = -150. ! Level of interface of fine and coarse soil layer [-1d4..0 cm, R]

* In case IPOS = 3 or 4, specify also
KVTOP = 5.0   ! Vertical hydraulic conductivity top layer, [0..1000 cm/d, R]
KVBOT = 10.0  ! Vertical hydraulic conductivity bottom layer, [0..1000 cm/d, R]

* In case IPOS = 5, specify also
GEOFAC = 4.8  ! Geometry factor of Ernst, [0..100 -, R]
```

The most important parameters that should be known or estimated from the drainage setup are the spacing, depth and wet perimeter of the drains. The depth of the impervious layers should be given. Further, depending on the drain position, vertical and horizontal hydraulic conductivity values need to be specified.

The shape factor (SHAPE), drain entry resistance (ENTRES) and the hydraulic conductivity values are subject of calibration.

3.6. Initial and boundary conditions

3.6.1. Initial conditions

Depending on the processes involved in the simulation, the following initial conditions can be specified:

- I. Initial soil moisture condition (*.swp, soil water section, part 1) – obligatory
- II. Initial snow water equivalent (*.swp, soil water section, part 9; if SWSNOW = 1) – optional; needed, if snow accumulation and melt is calculated
- III. Initial soil temperature profile (*.swp, heat flow section, part 4) – optional; needed, if heat flow is calculated using numerical method
- IV. Initial solute concentration (*.swp, solute section, part 2) – optional; needed, if the simulation includes solute transport

The most important and obligatory initial conditions are those for soil moisture conditions. These can be specified in three different ways.

One can specify the pressure head as a function of soil depth (SWINCO=1). If the pressure head is unknown, but if measured data on soil water content for the starting day is available, the pressure head can be calculated by using the water retention characteristics of the relevant layer of the soil profile. Data should be provided in table format, in the *.swp file (see above) indicating the depth (ZI) and the pressure head (H) values for the different soil layers:

```
* Part 1: Initial soil moisture condition

SWINCO = 2 ! Switch, type of initial soil moisture condition:
! 1 = pressure head as function of soil depth
! 2 = pressure head of each compartment is in hydrostatic equilibrium
!   with initial groundwater level
! 3 = read final pressure heads from output file of previous Swap simulation

* If SWINCO = 1, specify soil depth ZI [-1.d5..0 cm, R] and initial
* soil water pressure head H [-1.d10..1.d4 cm, R] (maximum MACP):

  ZI   H
  -0.5  -93.0
  -195.0 120.0
* End of table

* If SWINCO = 2, specify initial groundwater level:
GWLI = -75.0 ! Initial groundwater level [-10000..1000 cm, R]

* If SWINCO = 3, specify output file with initial values for current run:
INIFIL = 'result.end' ! name of output file *.END which contains initial values [A200]
```

If no measured data is available, it is a common practice to start the simulations right after the winter period, assuming field capacity (FC) conditions in the soil after snowmelt, and thus using $h=-200$ cm for all the soil layers.

If the initial groundwater level is known, and the conditions of hydrostatic equilibrium are valid, the 2nd option (SWINCO=2) could be chosen, and the model will calculate the initial conditions from the initial groundwater level (GWLI).

It is also possible to read the h values from a previous SWAP simulation run (SWINCO=3).

3.6.2. Boundary conditions

The upper boundary conditions of the SWAP model are defined by the atmospheric conditions. The bottom boundary conditions are defined in the bottom boundary section of the *.swp file. They can be provided in a separate file, having an extension *.bbc (see the previous SWAP versions), or directly in the *.swp file, as follows:

- I. Prescribe groundwater level
- II. Prescribe bottom flux
- III. Calculate bottom flux from hydraulic head of deep aquifer
- IV. Calculate bottom flux as function of groundwater level
- V. Prescribe soil water pressure head of bottom compartment
- VI. Bottom flux equals zero
- VII. Free drainage of soil profile
- VIII. Free outflow at soil-air interface

For condition I, the groundwater level should be given as a function of time. This lower boundary condition is relevant for soils with shallow groundwater table and huge influence of groundwater fluctuation on soil water regime.

In case of condition II, the bottom flux should be given in a table format (in cm/day, as a function of time) or the parameters of a sinus function should be defined. However, we do not recommend the use of this option for the OPTAIN modellers, as little is known about the fluxes at the bottom of the soil profile.

Options III and IV are recommended only if relevant information about the deep aquifer and hydrogeological surveys or modelling exists (III) or there is information on the relationship between the groundwater level and bottom flux (IV).

Option V can be relevant, if soil pressure gauges or soil water content sensors are installed at the bottom of the soil profile. In this case, those records can be used as bottom boundary condition.

Option VI assumes zero flux at the bottom of the soil profile. Such situation can occur if a water impermeable layer lays directly under the bottom of a relatively shallow soil profile.

Option VII can be used for deep soil profiles with relatively good water penetration. In this case, the model will calculate the amount of water, leaving the soil profile from incoming fluxes and soil properties.

Option VIII is the free outflow (seepage face). In this case, drainage will occur if the pressure head in the bottom compartment becomes larger than zero. This option is commonly applied for lysimeters, where outflow only occurs when the lowest part of the lysimeter becomes saturated. In the field this condition is appropriate when the soil profile is drained by a coarse gravel layer.

4. Setting up a SWAP project

The simplest way to start a new SWAP project is to open an existing *.swp file used for SWAP v4.x and to start rewriting it. The name of the file should be changed first. Below we follow the most important steps of setting up a new SWAP project.

4.1. General section of the *.swp file

The general section contains the main paths and settings of the SWAP Project:

Part 1. Environment, containing the main paths to input and output file folders

```
* Part 1: Environment (EXAMPLE)
PROJECT = 'Krakstad' ! Project description [A80]
PATHWORK = './results/' ! Path to work folder [A80]
PATHATM = 'meteo/' ! Path to folder with weather files [A80]
PATHCROP = 'crop/' ! Path to folder with crop files [A80]
PATHDRAIN = 'drain/' ! Path to folder with drainage files [A80]
SWSCRE = 1 ! Switch, display progression of simulation run to screen:
! 0 = no display to screen
! 1 = display water balance components
! 2 = display daynumber
SWERROR = 1 ! Switch for printing errors to screen [Y=1, N=0]
```

As SWAP requires separate meteorological input files for each year, and separate crop files for each crop, it is convenient to store the different file types in separate folders. Still, SWAP handles the location of the input files flexibly, and the user is free to design the file structure.

We recommend keeping SWERROR on (=1), as this helps in discovering the reasons of unfinished/failed/instable model runs.

Part 2. Simulation period

The start and the end date of the simulation period should be given in appropriate format. Meteorological input data must be available for the whole simulation period.

```
* Part 2: Simulation period
*
TSTART = 01-jan-2017 ! Start date of simulation run, give day-month-year [dd-mmm-yyyy]
TEND = 30-mar-2019 ! End date of simulation run, give day-month-year [dd-mmm-yyyy]
```

Part 3. Output dates

The output dates section might seem to be complicated at first glance, as it offers a wide range of options. But after defining the switches according to the needs, some options become invalid, and the rest is simple to design. One can specify daily and sub-daily output intervals; the latter being recommended if sub-daily meteorological input data is used. Apart of regular output intervals, output can be stored for specific dates.

For the OPTAIN field-scale modellers, daily output data is needed for model calibration and evaluation of the results. Therefore, below we show an example with daily output intervals, plus yearly output times for overall water and solute balances:

* Part 3: Output dates

* Number of output times during a day

NPRINTDAY = 1 - ! Number of output times during a day [1..1000, I]

* If NPRINTDAY = 1, specify dates for output of state variables and fluxes

SWMONTH = 0 ! Switch, output each month [Y=1, N=0]

* If SWMONTH = 0, choose output interval and/or specific dates

PERIOD = 1 ! Fixed output interval, ignore = 0, [0..366, I]

SWRES = 0 ! Switch, reset output interval counter each year [Y=1, N=0]

SWODAT = 0 ! Switch, extra output dates are given in table below [Y=1, N=0]

* If SWODAT = 1, list specific dates [dd-mmm-yyyy], maximum MAOUT dates:

OUTDATINT =

31-Jan-2017

31-Dec-2017

* End of table

* Output times for overall water and solute balances in *.BAL and *.BLC file: choose output

* at a fixed date each year or at different dates:

SWYRVAR = 0 ! 0 = each year output at the same date

! 1 = output at different dates

* If SWYRVAR = 0 specify fixed date:

DATEFIX = 31 12 ! Specify day and month for output of yearly balances [dd mm]

* If SWYRVAR = 1 specify all output dates [dd-mmm-yyyy], maximum MAOUT dates:

OUTDAT =

31-dec-2017

31-dec-2018

* End of table

If the user wants to have hourly outputs, NPRINTDAY should be set to 24, but any other time intervals within a day can be given up to 1000 records per day. In the above example, the output interval is fixed to get yearly balances, using the SWYRVAR and DATEFIX switches.

Part 4. Output files

In this section one can specify different output files of the SWAP model runs. The output file structure is rather complex; one can request formatted or unformatted hydrological data in the output. Below we list the types of files, available as model outputs.

Part 4: Output files

* General information

OUTFIL = 'Result' ! Generic file name of output files [A16]

SWHEADER = 0 ! Print header at the start of each balance period [Y=1, N=0]

* **SWHEADER SHOULD BE 0, FOR CLEAN FORMAT**

* Optional files

SWVAP = 1 ! Switch, **output soil profiles of moisture, solute and temperature** [Y=1, N=0]

SWBLC = 1 ! Switch, **output file with detailed yearly water balance** [Y=1, N=0]

SWATE = 0 ! Switch, **output file with soil temperature profiles** [Y=1, N=0]

SWBMA = 0 ! Switch, **output file with water fluxes, only for macropore flow** [Y=1, N=0]

SWDRF = 1 ! Switch, **output of drainage fluxes, only for extended drainage** [Y=1, N=0]

SWSWB = 1 ! Switch, **output surface water reservoir, only for extended drainage** [Y=1, N=0]

To have a common file structure and output files that can be easily used for validating the SWAT+ results, for the OPTAIN field-scale modellers it is recommended to:

- Specify OUTFIL so that the name of the output files would reflect the name of the pilot fields
- Keep SWHEADER zero, so that the output files could be more easily processed
- Set SWVAP and SWBAL equal to 1
- Set SWDRF and SWSWB equal to 0 (none of the case studies use the extended drainage option)
- To set SWMBA equal to 1 only in case, if the macropore option was used for calibrating the model

4.2. Meteorological section of the *.swp file

The file name of the meteorological input data corresponds to the weather station, whilst the extensions show the year, as explained in the example below.

```
* General data

* File name
METFIL = 'Krakstad' ! File name of meteorological data without extension .YYY, [A200]
                ! Extension is equal to last 3 digits of year, e.g., 003 denotes year 2003

* Type of weather data for potential evapotranspiration
SWETR = 0        ! 0 = Use basic weather data and apply Penman-Monteith equation
                ! 1 = Use reference evapotranspiration data in combination with crop factors

* If SWETR = 0, specify:
LAT   = 63.49    ! Latitude of meteo station [-90..90 degrees, R, North = +]
ALT   = 49.0     ! Altitude of meteo station [-400..3000 m, R]
ALTW  = 2.0      ! Height of wind speed measurement above soil surface (10 m is default) [0..99 m, R]
ANGSTROMA = 0.25 ! Fraction of extra-terrestrial radiation reaching the earth on overcast days [0..1 -, R]
ANGSTROMB = 0.50 ! Additional fraction of extra-terrestrial radiation reaching the earth on clear days [0..1 -, R]

SWDIVIDE = 1     ! 0 = Distribution E and T based on crop and soil factors
                ! 1 = Distribution E and T based on direct application of Penman-Monteith

* Time interval of evapotranspiration and rainfall weather data
SWMETDETAIL = 0 ! 0 = time interval is equal to one day
                ! 1 = time interval is less than one day

* In case of detailed meteorological weather records (SWMETDETAIL = 1), specify:
NMETDETAIL = 24 ! Number of weather data records each day [1..96 -, I]

* In case of daily meteorological weather records (SWMETDETAIL = 0):
SWETSINE = 0     ! Switch, distribute daily Tp and Ep according to sinus wave [Y=1, N=0]
```

If reference (measured) potential evapotranspiration data are available, there is an option to use those in the water balance calculations, by setting SWETR to one. Otherwise, the latitude, altitude and other parameters must be specified. The ANSTROMA and ANGSTROMB parameters can be looked up in the databases of the local meteorological centres or can be calibrated if the model turns out to be sensitive against those. The other option is to use the [FAO calculation scheme for radiation components](#).

Further, the modellers should make decisions on the within day distribution of the weather records. In case of daily weather data, we recommend leaving the default values. In case of detailed weather records, the number of records per day must be specified. Further information on within-day precipitation data options is given in subchapter 3.1.2 of this protocol.

4.3. Crop section of the *.swp file

If the input data is prepared properly as described in chapter 3, the crop section of the main SWAP input file does not need additional settings. Thus, the crop section of the *.swp file consists of the crop rotation scheme (Part 1) and fixed irrigation applications (Part 2). Parts 1 and 2 are described in sub-chapters 3.3.1 and 3.3.4, respectively.

4.4. Soil water section of the *.swp file

The soil water section is the most extended section of the SWAP main input file. It consists of the following nine parts:

- Part 1. Initial soil moisture conditions (*described in sub-chapter 3.5.1*)
- Part 2. Ponding, runoff and runon
- Part 3. Soil evaporation
- Part 4. Vertical discretization of the soil profile (*described in sub-chapter 3.2.1*)
- Part 5. Soil hydraulic functions (*described in sub-chapters 3.2.2 and 3.2.3*)
- Part 6. Hysteresis of soil water retention functions
- Part 7. Maximum rooting depth
- Part 8. Preferential flow due to macropores (*practical guidelines are given in Sub-chapter 6.4*)
- Part 9. Snow and frost
- Part 10. Numerical solution of Richards' equation for soil water flow

Further, we focus on the key switches and parameters needed to setup a SWAP project that were not introduced in the previous chapters.

Part 2. Ponding, runoff and runon

Water ponding, runoff and runon parameters determine the amount of water, stagnating on the surface and surface runoff. Water ponding is driven by the ponding threshold for runoff, which is the maximum thickness of water that can be stored on the surface without generating surface runoff. Ponding water will partly evaporate, partly infiltrate in the soil. This is an important parameter for flat areas, and can be set to zero, or values close to zero (depending on surface roughness) for slopes.

The ponding threshold is expressed in cm of water column and can be constant (SWPOND_{MX}=0) or dynamic (SWPOND_{MX}=1). In the latter case, the minimum thickness for runoff, POND_{MX}_{TB} is defined as a function of time.

The runoff parameters RSRO and RSROEXP are empirical parameters of the surface runoff equation (Eq. 4.2, page 58, Kores et al., 2017), and must be calibrated:

$$q_{\text{runoff}} = \frac{1}{\gamma} \left(\max(0, (h_0 - h_{0,\text{threshold}})) \right)^\beta$$

- Where: q_{runoff} - surface runoff flux (cm day⁻¹)
 h_0 - ponding depth of water (cm)
 $h_{0,\text{threshold}}$ - critical depth of water (cm)
 γ - resistance parameter (RSRO in the *.swp file)
 β - exponent in the empirical relation (-) (RSROEXP in the *.swp file)

* Part 2: Ponding, runoff and runon

* Ponding

* Switch for variation ponding threshold for runoff
 SWPOND μ X = 0 ! 0 = Ponding threshold for runoff is constant
 ! 1 = Ponding threshold for runoff varies in time

* If SWPOND μ X = 0, specify
POND μ X = 0.0 ! In case of ponding, minimum thickness for runoff [0..1000 cm, R]

* If SWPOND μ X = 1, specify minimum thickness for runoff POND μ X τ B [0..1000 cm, R] as function of time
DATE μ X POND μ X τ B ! (max. MAIRG records)
 01-jan-2017 0.2
 31-dec-2019 0.2

* End of table

* Runoff
RSRO = 0.01 ! Drainage resistance for surface runoff [0.001..1.0 d, R]
RSROEXP = 0.9 ! Exponent in drainage equation of surface runoff [0.01..10.0 -, R]

* Runon: specify whether runon data are provided in extra input file
 SWRUNON = 0 ! 0 = No input of runon data
 ! 1 = Runon data are provided in extra input file

* If SWRUNON = 1, specify name of file with runon input data
 * This file may be an output file *.inc (with only 1 header line) of a previous Swap-simulation
 RUFIL = 'runon.inc' ! File name with extension [A80]

If there is information about surface runon, such data can be provided in a separate file, indicating the dates and amounts of water, reaching the soil surface of the study area.

Part 3. Soil evaporation

When the soil is wet, soil evaporation equals its potential rate; this is also the case with ponded conditions. When the soil becomes drier, the soil hydraulic conductivity decreases, which reduces the potential to the actual evaporation rate. In SWAP the maximum evaporation rate that the topsoil can sustain, E_{max} (cm d⁻¹), is calculated according to Darcy's law (Kroes et al., 2017):

$$E_{\max} = K_{1/2} \left(\frac{h_{\text{atm}} - h_1 - z_1}{z_1} \right)$$

Where: E_{\max} - maximum evaporation rate that the soil can sustain (cm day⁻¹)
 $K_{1/2}$ - average hydraulic conductivity between the soil surface and the first node (cm day⁻¹)
 h_{atm} - soil water pressure head in equilibrium with air relative humidity (cm)
 h_1 - soil water pressure head at the first node (cm)
 z_1 - soil depth at the first node (cm)

Note that the value of E_{\max} depends on the thickness of the topsoil compartments. Increase of compartment thickness generally results in smaller values of E_{\max} due to smaller hydraulic head gradients. For accurate simulations at extreme hydrological conditions, the thickness of the top compartments should not be more than 1 cm (Van Dam and Feddes, 2000). This concerns the discretisation of the soil profile: the thickness of the basic calculation units (HCOMP, Figure 7) should preferably be 1 cm for the upper 5-10 cm soil layer.

The limitation of the above described E_{\max} calculation procedure is that it is governed by the soil hydraulic functions (pF-curve and K-function, see sub-chapter 3.2.2). It is still not clear to which extent the soil hydraulic functions are valid for the top few centimetres of a soil, which are subject to splashing rain, dry crust formation, root extension, and various cultivation practices. Therefore, empirical evaporation functions may be used, which require calibration of their parameters for local climate, soil, cultivation practices, and drainage situation (Kroes et al, 2017). SWAP offers the option to choose between the empirical evaporation functions of Black et al. (1969) or Boesten and Stroosnijder (1986). The latter method was developed for temperate climate.

The SWREDU switch can be used to choose the method used for reducing potential soil evaporation, as presented below:

* Part 3: Soil evaporation

CFEVAPPOND = 1.25 ! When ETref is used, evaporation coefficient in case of ponding [0..3 -, R]

SWCFBS = 0 ! Switch for use of soil factor CFBS to calculate Epot from ETref
 ! 0 = soil factor is not used
 ! 1 = soil factor is used

* If SWCFBS = 1, specify soil factor CFBS:

CFBS = 0.5 ! Soil factor CFBS in Epot = CFBS * ETref [0..1.5 -, R]

* If SWDIVIDE = 1 (partitioning according to PMdirect) specify minimum soil resistance

RSOIL = 30.0 ! Soil resistance of wet soil [0..1000.0 s/m, R]

SWREDU = 1 ! Switch, method for reduction of potential soil evaporation:

! 0 = reduction to maximum Darcy flux

! 1 = reduction to maximum Darcy flux and to maximum Black (1969)

! 2 = reduction to maximum Darcy flux and to maximum Boesten/Stroosnijder (1986)

COFRED = 0.35 ! Soil evaporation coefficient of Black [0..1 cm/d^{1/2}, R],
 ! or Boesten/Stroosnijder [0..1 cm^{1/2}, R]

RSIGNI = 0.5 ! Minimum rainfall to reset method of Black [0..1 cm/d, R]

SWAP will determine the actual evaporation by taking the minimum value of the potential evaporation, E_{\max} and, if selected by the user, one of the empirical functions. Default soil evaporation coefficient for Black (COFRED) equals $0.35 \text{ cm d}^{-0.5}$, and for Boesten-Stroosnijder, $0.54 \text{ cm}^{-0.5}$.

Other parameters present in the soil evaporation section are also subject to calibration:

CFEVAPPOND: Refers to conditions, when the reference potential evapotranspiration (ET_{ref}) data are given in the meteorological input files (Table 3, Figure 4) and are used for calculating the water balance elements (switch $SWETR=1$, see sub-chapter 4.2). In this case the evaporation from the ponding water is not calculated by the Penman-Monteith (PM) method, but derived empirically from ET_{ref} , so the evaporation coefficient must be given.

SWCFBS: Can be used to transform reference crop evapotranspiration into potential soil evaporation. Commonly a soil factor (CFBS) of 0.5 is used.

SWDIVIDE: As described before, partitioning of potential evapotranspiration and evaporation fluxes can be based on crop and soil factors, or on direct application of the PM equation. With the switch $SWDIVIDE$ (see sub-chapter 4.2) the user selects the preferred method. If $SWDIVIDE=1$ and the PM method is used, the minimum soil resistance (RSOL) must be given. Note, that generally the PM method is the preferred one; ET_{ref} could be used optionally, if some of the data needed to calculate potential evapotranspiration based on the PM equation are missing or unreliable.

Part 6. Hysteresis of soil water retention functions

Hysteresis refers to non-uniqueness of the $\Theta(h)$ (moisture content-tension) relation (Hillel, 1980; Feddes et al., 1988), which is related to the phenomenon that soils hold more water at a given tension during desorption than during sorption.

Commonly, the soil water retention curves are determined in laboratory conditions from pre-saturated, undisturbed soil samples. Thus, the measured $\Theta(h)$ relationship corresponds to drying conditions. The process is demonstrated in Figure 13. Gradual desorption of an initially saturated soil sample gives the main drying curve, while slow absorption of an initially dry sample results in the main wetting curve. In the field, partly wetting and drying occurs in numerous cycles, resulting in so-called drying and wetting scanning curves lying between the main drying and the main wetting curves (Kroes et al., 2017).

Setting $SWHYST$ to 1 or 2 will turn on the hysteresis option of the SWAP model with wetting or drying initial conditions, respectively:

* Part 6: Hysteresis of soil water retention function

* Switch for hysteresis:

$SWHYST = 0$! 0 = no hysteresis
 ! 1 = hysteresis, initial condition wetting
 ! 2 = hysteresis, initial condition drying

* If $SWHYST = 1$ or 2, specify:

$TAU = 0.2$! Minimum pressure head difference to change from wetting to drying and vice versa, [0..1 cm, R]

Figure 13. Water retention curve with hysteresis, showing the main wetting, main drying and scanning curves (after Kroes et al., 2017).

The main soil hydraulic properties (soil water section, part 5., described in sub-chapter 3.2.2) are defined for drying initial conditions. If SWHYST \neq 0, the parameter ALFAW will be active and must be defined as correctly as possible, and calibrated.

Part 7. Maximum rooting depth

The maximum rooting depth can be identified using the soil profile information. In case of a heavily compacted soil layer, or impervious layer at the bottom of the soil profile, the maximum rooting depth must be set to the depth of those layers. If there are no constraints for root development, the maximum possible value can be used.

* Part 7: Maximum rooting depth

RDS = 80.0 ! Maximum rooting depth allowed by the soil profile [1..5000 cm, R]

Part 9. Snow and frost

Winter conditions are important in all the case studies involved in the OPTAIN project. The options for snow and frost can only be used when the soil temperature simulation is activated (SWHEA=1).

Further, SWAP will calculate snow melt if the switch SWSNOW is set to 1.

When the snow option is switched on, SWAP simulates snowfall, snow accumulation, and the water balance of the snowpack. For this, the initial conditions (SNOWINCO) and three parameters must be defined (TEPRRAIN, TEPRSNOW and SNOWCOEF). All the three snow parameters are subject to calibration, especially the snowmelt calibration factor (also called in other models as degree day factor for snowmelt).

If the option for frost is activated (SWFORST=1), SWAP simulates freezing of soil water when soil temperature drops below a threshold value, defined by the TFRSOTSTA parameter. The fraction of free volumetric soil water content is described as a linear

function of soil temperature between the two threshold temperatures of TFROSTSTA and TFROSTEND. These parameters can be calibrated.

Part 9: Snow and frost

```
* Snow
SWSNOW = 1          ! Switch, calculate snow accumulation and melt [Y=1, N=0]

* If SWSNOW = 1, specify:
SNOWINCO = 22.0    ! Initial snow water equivalent [0..1000 cm, R]
TEPRRAIN = 2.0     ! Temperature above which all precipitation is rain [ 0..10 ºC, R]
TEPRSNOW = -2.0    ! Temperature below which all precipitation is snow [-10..0 ºC, R]
SNOWCOEF = 0.3     ! Snowmelt calibration factor [0.0...10.0 -, R]

* Frost
SWFROST = 0        ! Switch, in case of frost reduce soil water flow [Y=1, N=0]

* If SWFROST = 1, specify soil temperature range in which soil water flow is reduced
TFROSTSTA = 0.0    ! Soil temperature (ºC) at which reduction of water fluxes starts [-10..5 ºC, R]
TFROSTEND = -1.0   ! Soil temperature (ºC) at which reduction of water fluxes ends [-10..5 ºC, R]
```

In case of soil ice, the following parameters are adjusted (for details, see Chapter 10, Kroes et al., 2017):

- Soil hydraulic conductivity
- Actual crop water uptake
- Drainage fluxes at all drainage levels
- Bottom flux
- Boundary fluxes.

Part 10. Numerical solution of Richards' equation for soil water flow

The parameters of the numerical solution may be changed in case of model instability. Generally, these parameters are well-defined and advanced knowledge on numerical solutions is needed for re-defining their values.

4.5. Heat flow section of the *.swp file

The SWAP model can calculate heat flow through the soil profile and between the soil layers. Though this section is optional, it is recommended to use it for the OPTAIN case studies, especially if soil temperature data is available for calibrating the heat flow section of the model. Soil temperature simulations are needed for calculating winter hydrological conditions and for more precise calculation of evaporation.

The heat flow section can be activated by setting the SWHEA switch to 1. SWAP offers two different approaches for calculating heat flow and soil temperature: an analytical approach (SWCALT=1) and a numerical approach (SWCALT=2).

When the analytical method is used, the parameters describing the soil surface temperature wave and the damping depth (DDAMP) should be specified:

```

*****
* Part 1: Specify whether simulation includes heat flow

SWHEA = 1 ! Switch for simulation of heat transport [Y=1, N=0]
*****
* Part 2: Heat flow calculation method

* Switch for calculation method
SWCALT = 1 ! 1 = analytical method
                ! 2 = numerical method
*****
* Part 3: Analytical method

* In case of the analytical method (SWCALT = 1) specify:
TAMPLI = 10.0 ! Amplitude of annual temperature wave at soil surface [0..50 C, R]
TMEAN = 15.0 ! Mean annual temperature at soil surface [-10..30 C, R]
TIMREF = 90.0 ! Time at which the sinus temperature wave reaches it's top [0..366.0 d, R]
DDAMP = 50.0 ! Damping depth of soil temperature wave [1..500 cm, R]

```

The parameters of the soil surface temperature wave are: TAMPLI, TMEAN and TIMREF. If measurements of soil surface temperature exist, these parameters can be derived and further fine-tuned during the model calibration.

The damping depth can be calculated from the following equation:

$$DDAMP = \sqrt{\frac{2 * D_{heat}}{\omega}}$$

Where: D_{heat} - soil thermal diffusivity ($cm^2 day^{-1}$); can be taken from Table 4.
 ω - angular frequency, defined as $2\pi / \tau$
 τ - period of the wave (day)

Table 4. Thermal diffusivity D_{heat} ($cm^2 day^{-1}$) for various dry and wet soils (Jury et al., 1991)

Sand		Loam		Clay		Peat	
Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet
147	380	156	518	156	320	112	104

When the numerical method is used for heat flow calculations, information should be given on soil texture, initial soil temperature and type of bottom boundary condition. Soil texture is defined as the fraction of sand, silt, clay, and organic matter content for each soil layer:

```

* Part 4: Numerical method

* In case of the numerical method (SWCALT = 2) specify:

* Specify for each physical soil layer the soil texture (g/g mineral parts) and organic matter content (g/g dry soil):

ISOILLAY PSAND PSILT PCLAY ORGMAT ! (maximum MAHO records)
1      0.80  0.15  0.05  0.100
2      0.80  0.15  0.05  0.100
3      0.80  0.15  0.05  0.100
4      0.80  0.15  0.05  0.100
* End of table

```

Where MAHO stands for maximum number of soil horizons. The textural classes are defined as sand (grain size between 63 μm and 2 mm), silt (grain size between 63 and 2 μm) and clay (grain size below 2 μm).

The initial conditions are defined in table format, as the average soil temperature of each soil layer:

* If SWINCO = 1 or 2, list initial temperature TSOIL [-50..50 ^\circ C , R] as function of soil depth ZH [-1.0d5..0 cm, R]:

ZH	TSOIL	!	(maximum MACP records)
-10.0	15.0		
-40.0	12.0		
-70.0	10.0		
-95.0	9.0		

* End of table

Where ZH is the soil depth, and MACP stands for maximum number of soil compartments.

The top boundary conditions can be either taken from the air temperature values (SwTopbHea=1), or from soil temperature measurements at the soil surface (SwTopbHea=2).

In the latter case, the measured soil temperature values should be specified as a function of time in a separate file, having an extension *.tss:

* Define top boundary condition:

SwTopbHea = 1 !1 = use air temperature of meteo input file as top boundary
 !2 = use measured top soil temperature as top boundary

* If SwTopbHea = 2, specify name of input file with soil surface temperatures
 TSOILFILE = 'Krakstad' ! File name without extension .TSS, [A16]

Two options are offered for bottom boundary conditions: zero heat flux at the bottom of the soil profile (SwBotbHea=1) or defined soil temperature at the bottom (SwBotbHea=2):

* Define bottom boundary condition:

SwBotbHea = 1 !1 = no heat flux; 2 = prescribe bottom temperature

* If SwBotbHea = 2, specify bottom boundary temperature TBOT [-50..50 ^\circ C , R] as function of date [dd-mm-yyyy]:

DATE	TBOT	!	(maximum MABBC records)
01-jan-2002	-15.0		
30-jun-2002	-20.0		
23-dec-2002	-10.0		

* End of table

The first option could be used if we can assume no or minor heat flux at the bottom of the soil profile during the simulation period. The second option assumes that soil temperature sensors are installed at the bottom of the soil profile.

Generally, for the OPTAIN case studies it is recommended to use the heat flow calculation option of the SWAP model, using the analytical method (SWCALT=1). Measured soil temperature data is to be used to define the initial conditions for the heat flow routine. If no such data is available from the field, observed data from similar fields or neighbouring meteorological stations could be used.

It is recommended to use the air temperature as a top boundary condition (SwTopbHea=1), as soil temperature is commonly not measured directly on the soil surface. Also, this would allow similar settings across the case studies.

Concerning bottom boundary conditions, the best option is to use soil temperature data measured at the bottom of the soil profile directly in the reference soil profile, or at the nearest meteorological station. Soil temperature is relatively easy to measure compared to soil water content, hence, such data is commonly available for modelling studies.

5. Reference data

5.1. Types of reference data

SWAP, as all soil hydrological models, incorporates empirical and semi-empirical elements and sources of uncertainty, therefore the model must be calibrated. There are different types of reference data that can be used for calibrating the water and temperature routines of the SWAP model:

1. Soil water content dynamics
2. Evaporation, transpiration
3. Surface runoff
4. Drainage outflow
5. Soil temperature dynamics
6. Crop yield

The most used reference data are the soil water content, soil temperature and drainage outflow. Evaporation and transpiration are hard to measure continuously, while experiments focusing on soil water regime are rarely equipped with surface runoff measuring devices. Crop yield could be used as reference data when the detailed crop model WOFOST is applied.

In the OPTAIN project, soil temperature, soil water content and drainage outflow (where relevant) will be used for model calibration. Information on typical values of evaporation, transpiration and surface runoff will be considered at soft-calibration level. Thus, the simulated values will be compared with reference values available from the area using expert-based evaluation.

5.2. Reference data quality check

Soil water content (SWC) is traditionally measured by different sensors/probes installed in the representative soil layers. The measurement accuracy of such probes depends on the sensor technique, which is sensitive to soil characteristics such as soil texture, temperature, bulk density, and salinity. However, the calibration functions provided by instrument manufacturers are generally developed under laboratory conditions, and their accuracy for field applications is rarely investigated (Mittelbach et al., 2012). Studies comparing the performance of such sensors concluded that i) sensors from different manufacturers are capable to capture the changes in soil moisture dynamics of the reference method, but can differ significantly in absolute values measured and ii) in-field calibration of soil moisture probes is highly recommended (Mittelbach et al., 2012; Leib et al., 2003). This indicates that a reference data quality check is needed before starting the model calibration. The reference data quality check consists of the following steps:

- **Soil temperature** dynamics should be in line with the air temperature (graphical check)
- **Soil water content**

The measured SWC of each soil layer must be cross validated with the soil water retention curve corresponding to the same layer (Figure 14.) as follows:

- In non-frozen soils, SWC should not be far below the wilting point, as such conditions hardly exist in the nature. The wilting point (WP) is defined as the soil water content corresponding to the water potential of $pF=4.2$. Thus, all the SWC values below $\approx pF=4.4$ should be carefully checked and possibly blacklisted. In Figure 14, Θ at $pF=4.4$ equals $0.2 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$, therefore the soil water content values in the lower white circle should be blacklisted (data from July).
- SWC should not be high above the total porosity / saturated water content (OSAT) of the soil. Up to 5-7 vol% difference is acceptable, but values above that should be checked individually. We can see one such peak in Figure 14 (upper white circle).
- If SWFROST = 0, (no freezing of soil water content is simulated), all the measured SWC values should be removed for periods when the soil is frozen. This is because the sensors measure the liquid phase of the water, whilst the model calculates the total water content, including the frozen part. So, the SWC measurements within the frozen soil cannot be used for model calibration. The low values can be removed via a cross-check with the soil temperature of the same layer, but a graphical representation of soil water content dynamics should clearly show the values that should be blacklisted.
- If SWFROST = 1, and the model accounts for the frozen and liquid part of the soil water, the measured data can be used for model calibration. However, not much experience is available for such exercises, and the sensors might similarly fail under freezing conditions. Therefore, it is recommended to carry out separate model calibration for winter conditions, handling the SWC measured in frozen soils separately from other periods of the year.

Figure 14. Graphical presentation of the quality check for observed soil water content

5.3. Script for reference data quality check

Within the OPTAIN project, the reference data quality check was automatized in an R environment.

The input file for running the code is an Excel workbook, containing i) the ID of the soil layer and corresponding wilting point and saturated water content (Worksheet 1, Figure 15. left); ii) the observed data to be checked (Worksheets 2-11, Figure 15, right).

Figure 15. Wilting point (column suction42) and saturated water content (column tethas), of different soil layers of the reference sites. F, G, A, V are the site name, 15, 40, etc. is the depth of the soil moisture probes (left); Reference worksheet for observed data- W- soil water content, T- soil temperature, ta – air temperature (right)

The R-script incorporates direct instructions on how to adjust and run the code (Figure 16). The data series can be plotted for visual analyses. The demo version is available for the OPTAIN partners and is being upgraded upon their requests.


```

1 #####
2 ## ##### Data Quality Check ##### ##
3 #####
4 #####
5 ## Guidelines
6 #####
7 ## -Run these commands line by line!
8 ## -You may skip the modifications of the wilting point and saturated water content!
9 ## -If you want to play with setting up the blacklisted df_1 dataset, you must run the lines 50-60 after
10 ## -In line 75-83 you can get the density function of the given sites! It can help to decide how much you
11 ## -In line 87-91 you can save the blacklisted data and select a few to save if you see the necessity of
12 #####
13 #####
14 ##SWCs should be removed below the wilting point (WP (4.2))!
15 cat(
16   "\n====[Manually cleaning data]====\n",
17   "\n4.Soil water content should be removed below the wilting point!\n"
18 )
19 ##Blacklisted data!
20 df_1 <- subset(df_c,! (swc>suc42))
21
22
23 ##Data Overview!
24 site <- df_1 %>% dplyr::group_by(sites) %>% dplyr::summarise(length(sites)) %>% pull(sites)
25 dbs <- df_1 %>% dplyr::group_by(sites) %>% dplyr::summarise(length(sites)) %>% pull()
26
27 percent <- round((dbs/((dim(df_c)[1])/(length(unique(df_c$sites)))))*100,digits=3)
28
29 cat(
30   "\n[Summary]",
31   view(df_1)
32 )
33 df <- cbind(site,dbs,percent)
34

```

```

if(winDialog(type = c("yesno"), ...
install.packages(need)
lapply(need,require,character.on...
}
}
install.packages("learnr")
install.packages("shiny")
##Reading all files into a list!
input_data <- paste0("c:/Users/c...
source("C:/Users/csfa/Csillan/BO...

```

Name	Size	Modified
clean2.R	3.6 KB	Jul 26, 2022, 7:34 PM
clean_manual.R	12.7 KB	Jul 26, 2022, 7:29 PM
function.R	95.4 B	Jul 26, 2022, 7:33 PM
load (1).R	2.9 KB	Jul 26, 2022, 7:33 PM
load.R	2.9 KB	Jul 26, 2022, 7:41 PM
main.R	4.2 KB	Jul 26, 2022, 7:33 PM
input-csanza-demo.xlsx	531.1 KB	Jul 26, 2022, 7:34 PM

Figure 16. Inbuilt instructions for running the R-code for data quality check

6. Calibration of the SWAP model

In general, during the calibration of soil hydrological models we move from more integrated characteristics towards less integrated ones, both in space and time. Thus, the yearly sums of the soil water balance elements (evaporation, transpiration, runoff etc.) should be checked before starting the calibration of daily data. Similarly, differences between the simulated and measured total amounts of water stored in the soil profile should be minimised before looking into the water redistribution between the soil layers.

For the OPTAIN field-scale modellers, two scripts were developed and are being tested to support the calibration of the SWAP model. In the next sub-chapters, we give a short introduction of these tools.

6.1. The manual hard calibration and visualisation tool

The SWAP model does not feature a graphical user interface (GUI). It runs by command line and all inputs and outputs are stored as text files. These characteristics make it partly difficult to use, but at the same time easy to connect to other systems. The unprocessed output of SWAP is hard to read, even more when comparing it to measured reference data, or previous model runs under differing parameter settings. Additionally, the evaluation of the model performance requires using statistical indicators, such as the Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) (Nash & Sutcliffe 1970), which are not included in the base model. As SWAP does not have the inherent ability to accomplish these vital aspects of model calibration and verification on its own, work was begun within the OPTAIN project on an R-script for manual hard calibration and visualization. A detailed technical description of the tool is being developed; online support is available for OPTAIN field-scale modellers.

For using the manual hard calibration and visualisation tool (MHC tool), a specific folder structure should be created in a separate folder, as presented in Appendix 6. The SWAP input data files and the reference data should be copied to the relevant folders, entitled “SWAP” and “observed”. The MHC tool, in its present form, can handle two types of reference data: soil water content dynamics and drainage outflow. Observed data should be provided in Excel format according to the example in Appendix 6.

The MHC tool executes the SWAP model, reads the output and reformats it into a standardized format. To compare model output with measured reference data (such as soil moisture), the depth of the measured data must match the depth of the modelled output value. If this is not the case, the script recalculates the modelled values by picking the closest depth or averaging two depths if they are equidistant (the utilization of a more advanced method of interpolation is under consideration). To ensure compatibility with all the case study sites, this function was built in a flexible fashion and can therefore handle an unlimited quantity of measurements at any desired depth. An automatic backup of the processed output, as well as the input files and model parameters is created and stored in a dedicated directory. This allows for intercomparison of model runs as well as the ability to undo to a previous model setup.

Figure 17. Visualized output of soil moisture content (SMC) of the measured reference data (solid line) and SWAP model runs (dotted lines) at 15 cm depth. The green line is the latest model run, the purple line the previous model run. The model run name was altered to convey which parameter was changed. In this case an alteration of parameter VLMPSTSS from 0.5 to 0.025 reduced the ability of the model in predicting the drop in SMC during July 2018.

With the SWAP output reformatted and harmonized with the site-specific measurements, statistical indicators of model performance can be calculated. Currently in use is the aforementioned NSE, as well as R^2 and PBIAS (Moriasi et al., 2015). Additionally, and most importantly for manual hard calibration, the model output is plotted against the measured values to provide visual feedback on model performance, as seen in Figure 17. The user can choose to compare any number of past archived model runs with the current model set-up, thus being able to identify changes resulting from alterations made to the model setup. This can also be seen in Figure 17. Use of the R package “plotly” allows for interaction with the plot, including zooming, panning, comparison of point values, hiding specific time-series, and more.

Figure 18. Graphical comparison of NSE values of various runs. The solid-coloured column indicates the current model setup. Default nomenclature for previous model runs is the creation date, however this can be renamed as desired.

The calculated statistical indicators can be compared to previous model runs (Figure 18). This can be done for all indicators for all depths, as well as for an average of all depths. Comparison of statistical indicators allows the user to see which model setup had the best performance, and by how much it was improved.

Finally, the script opens the SWAP main file, allowing the user to make any desired alterations. This file can be saved and closed, and upon running the script once more, the altered setup will be added to the analysis, repeating the cycle. The model setups included in the analysis are controlled by adding or removing archives of the model setups in the archive directory.

In its current state, the tool is functional and useable yet still predominantly a proof of concept. More features are planned, such as comparison to other measurements and soil properties (i.e. precipitation events, pressure head). The tool is currently slow and inefficient, but this will be fixed in future releases. Moreover, ease of use will be improved, and a documentation will be provided in the finalized version. The use of Rmarkdown or Rshiny to provide a GUI is being considered. The tool will be upgraded and made publicly available after careful testing.

6.2. Linking the PEST automatic hard calibration tool to the SWAP model

The automatic hard calibration tool (AHC), developed within the OPTAIN project automates the process of model calibration by communicating with the model's inputs and outputs. Such a tool facilitates a large number (e.g. thousands) of model runs using systematically changed alternative parameterizations, and automates the evaluation of those model results against reference data and the identification of the best parameter set. The use of such a tool makes work more efficient, helps harmonize the workflow at each case study, and to document the parameter-space that has been tested. For instance, PEST is a model-independent software that can be used for parameter estimation, sensitivity and uncertainty analysis. PEST stands for "parameter estimation". Given its model-independent features, PEST can be used with any other model whose input and output files are text files. The software comprises two global optimizers, a basic sensitivity analyser, a utility facilitating parallel run management and other utility support programs. More details on PEST are covered by Doherty (2015), including the theory embodied in PEST and its utility support software.

PEST runs the SWAP model with an initial guess of the parameters, compares the model results with observations, adjusts selected parameters using an optimization algorithm, and runs the model again. The procedure of adjusting selected parameters continues until the difference between the model results and observations meets predefined criteria by user. PEST interacts with a model through the model's own input and output files. The general workflow of PEST and interactions with the SWAP model are illustrated in Figure 19.

Figure 19. General workflow of PEST and interactions with SWAP model. OF = Objective Function. Ins file = instruction file

Because PEST operates in a model-independent manner, it interacts with a model through the model's own input and output files. Hence, no programming is required to use PEST to calibrate a model. However, two scripts have been developed for SWAP-PEST integration to facilitate the autocalibration process in the project.

During parameter estimation or computing sensitivities of model outputs to parameters, PEST must run a model many times. It does this through a call to the operating system. Hence the model must be accessible to a user (and therefore to PEST) through the command line. PEST requires an executable file which can be called from a batch file for consecutive operations in calibration. The batch file is available in Appendix 7.

The objective function (OF), which is used for model calibration and performance analysis, should be calculated after each model run during the calibration process. To calculate the OF, a script (R and Python versions) that reads both SWAP model output and measured data was developed. This script must be called after each run; hence it must be defined in the batch file. SWAP and PEST have been integrated successfully and all required PEST files (control, template, and instructions files) and introductory documentation together with SWAP files are available for the OPTAIN partners.

6.3. SWAP model calibration

6.3.1. Practical recommendations on model calibration

The observation period should be subdivided into calibration and validation periods, the latter being shorter.

Considering the goals and purposes of the OPTAIN project and depending on the reference data available, we recommend following the next hierarchical steps in model calibration:

- 1) Soil heat regime: soil temperature dynamics in daily time step (expert-based soft calibration; MHC is being upgraded for soil temperature calibration)

- 2) Soil hydrology: water balance elements on a yearly base (expert-based soft calibration)
- 3) Soil hydrology: drainage outflow (MHC)
- 4) Soil hydrology: total amount of water, stored in the soil profile in daily time step (MHC)
- 5) Soil hydrology: soil water content dynamics of none-frozen soil in daily time step, starting from the bottom of the soil profile (MHC and AHC)
- 6) Soil hydrology: soil water content dynamics of frozen soil in a daily time step (MHC and AHC)

If observed soil temperature data are available, the **soil heat regime** is relatively easy to calibrate. This is done by tuning the parameters of the soil heat flow section to minimise the difference between the simulated and observed soil temperature dynamics, starting from the bottom of the soil profile. It is easier to calibrate the parameters for the deeper layers first, as soil temperature changes are less variable and driven by less complex processes in those layers, compared to the soil surface.

Checking the water balance elements on a yearly base can be done by evaluating the water balance components in the *.bal file. An example of such results is given in Figure 20.

The **soft calibration of the SWAP hydrological routine** consists of an expert evaluation of the water balance components, using all the available knowledge and information about reference site on evapotranspiration (transpiration plus soil evaporation), surface runoff and ratio of surface runoff and drainage outflow to total runoff.


```

File Edit Format View Help
Period      : 2018-01-01 until 2018-12-31
Depth soil profile : 160.00 cm

      Water storage
Final    :      66.50 cm
Initial  :      64.30 cm
=====
Change   :      2.20 cm

Water balance components (cm)

In                               Out
=====                         =====
Rain + snow :      89.17      Interception :      4.93
Runon       :      0.00      Runoff       :     10.05
Irrigation  :      0.00      Transpiration :     23.32
Bottom flux :      0.00      Soil evaporation :      2.11
                               Crack flux    :     15.54
                               Drainage level 1 :     31.02
=====                         =====
Sum         :      89.17      Sum          :     86.97
  
```

Figure 20. Yearly water balance components as calculated by the SWAP model

If the soil is drained and data on **drainage outflow** exists, those data should be compared with the simulated drainage outflow in daily time step to adjust the drainage parameters before calibrating the soil water content.

The next step of model calibration involves comparing the simulated and observed **amount of water, stored in the whole profile**, in a daily time step. For this, the amount of water stored in each of the soil layers should be summed up for each day by multiplying the observed soil water content (in $\text{cm}^3 \text{cm}^{-3}$) with the thickness of the soil layer (in cm), represented by the sensor. The total amount of water, stored in the soil profile is expressed in cm of water column. Further, the model parameters determining the hydrological processes (surface runoff, evaporation, transpiration, deep percolation, drainage etc.) should be tuned to minimize the difference between the observed and simulated amounts of water, stored in the soil profile. This step of calibration helps fine-tuning the water balance elements without caring about the redistribution of water within the soil profile.

The last step is the **hard calibration of the soil water content dynamics** of each observed layer for non-frozen and frozen periods. This can be the most time consuming and demanding step of the calibration process. At this stage, the type and the parameters of the soil hydraulic functions as well as the parameters of the soil macropore routine are the main calibration parameters.

6.3.2. Objective function

There are less well-defined objective functions for field-scale models as exist for catchment level models. The main reason for this is the absence of long-term time series of reference data for field-scale model calibration, as these observations are expensive and time consuming, and due to the lack of harmonised observation systems on soil hydrological data.

In their model evaluation paper, Moriasi et al. (2015) give performance measures for the field-scale models (Table 5) for the coefficient of determination (R^2) and index of agreement (d).

Table 5. Evaluation criteria for recommended statistical performance measures for watershed- and field-scale models (after Moriasi et al., 2015)

Measure	Output Response	Temporal Scale ^[a]	Performance Evaluation Criteria			
			Very Good	Good	Satisfactory	Not Satisfactory
Watershed scale						
R^2	Flow ^[b]	D-M-A	$R^2 > 0.85$	$0.75 < R^2 \leq 0.85$	$0.60 < R^2 \leq 0.75$	$R^2 \leq 0.60$
	Sediment/P ^[c]	M	$R^2 > 0.80$	$0.65 < R^2 \leq 0.80$	$0.40 < R^2 \leq 0.65$	$R^2 \leq 0.40$
	N	M	$R^2 > 0.70$	$0.60 < R^2 \leq 0.70$	$0.30 < R^2 \leq 0.60$	$R^2 \leq 0.30$
NSE	Flow	D-M-A	$NSE > 0.80$	$0.70 < NSE \leq 0.80$	$0.50 < NSE \leq 0.70$	$NSE \leq 0.50$
	Sediment	M	$NSE > 0.80$	$0.70 < NSE \leq 0.80$	$0.45 < NSE \leq 0.70$	$NSE \leq 0.45$
	N/P ^[c]	M	$NSE > 0.65$	$0.50 < NSE \leq 0.65$	$0.35 < NSE \leq 0.50$	$NSE \leq 0.35$
PBIAS (%)	Flow	D-M-A	$PBIAS < \pm 5$	$\pm 5 \leq PBIAS < \pm 10$	$\pm 10 \leq PBIAS < \pm 15$	$PBIAS \geq \pm 15$
	Sediment	D-M-A	$PBIAS < \pm 10$	$\pm 10 \leq PBIAS < \pm 15$	$\pm 15 \leq PBIAS < \pm 20$	$PBIAS \geq \pm 20$
	N/P ^[c]	D-M-A	$PBIAS < \pm 15$	$\pm 15 \leq PBIAS < \pm 20$	$\pm 20 \leq PBIAS < \pm 30$	$PBIAS \geq \pm 30$
Field scale						
R^2	Flow	M	$R^2 > 0.85$	$0.75 < R^2 \leq 0.85$	$0.70 < R^2 < 0.75$	$R^2 \leq 0.70$
d	Flow	M	$d > 0.90$	$0.85 < d \leq 0.90$	$0.75 < d < 0.85$	$d \leq 0.75$

^[a] D, M, and A denote daily, monthly, and annual temporal scales, respectively.

^[b] Includes stream flow, surface runoff, base flow, and tile flow, as appropriate, for watershed- and field-scale models.

^[c] Where there were no differences, PEC were grouped for the output responses.

Within the OPTAIN field-scale modelling team, it is strongly recommended to perform visual evaluation of the dynamics of measured and observed reference data (e.g., soil temperature and water content, drainage outflow) and to calculate the R^2 , d and NSE statistics (Nash and Sutcliffe, 1970), for performing model evaluation. O and P stand for observed and predicted values, respectively (Moriasi et al., 2015):

$$R^2 = \left[\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O})(P_i - \bar{P})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - \bar{P})^2}} \right]^2$$

$$NSE = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - P_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O})^2}$$

$$d = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - P_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (|P_i - \bar{O}| + |O_i - \bar{O}|)^2}$$

6.4. Model validation

The validation of the SWAP model will be performed, similarly to SWAT+, for an independent period, not within the calibration period. The length of the validation period is defined individually for each case study, depending on the length of available observations.

7. Scenario analyses in OPTAIN using the SWAP model

Besides other goals, the OPTAIN project aims at evaluating the effects of various NSWORMs on water regime, sediment, and nutrient fluxes at present and future climate conditions. The climate and management scenarios, implemented in the SWAT+ model will be introduced in the SWAP model to the highest extent possible, while considering the advantages and limitations of field-scale models.

The scenario analyses will be performed using calibrated and validated SWAP projects for each case study site. The OPTAIN field-scale modelling team will follow the same principles, as the SWAT+ modellers, described in Chapter 7 of the SWAT+ modelling protocol.

This chapter focuses on the peculiarities of implementing climate scenarios and NSWORMs in the SWAP model.

7.1. Implementation of climate scenarios in the SWAP model

The climate scenario dataset, developed by the WP3 team of the OPTAIN project and available on ZENODO (<https://zenodo.org/record/6202062#.Y3eNa3bMKUk>) contains both, gridded and point data. The latter were downscaled specifically for the SWAP pilot fields and contain all the weather variables needed to run the SWAP model in a daily time step. Data are available for a reference period (from 1981 to 2010) and future climate for periods from 2031 to 2060 and from 2071 to 2100.

The meteorological input data are derived for six GCM – RCM combinations and have been bias corrected for three RCPs (Table 6).

Table 6. List of future climate simulations selected for SWAP (and SWAT+) climate scenario runs in OPTAIN

Model ID number	Driving Model GCM	RCM	RCP's
1	EC-EARTH	CCLM4-8-17	
2	EC-EARTH	HIRHAM5	
3	HadGEM2-ES	HIRHAM5	2.6
4	HadGEM2-ES	RACMO22E	4.5 8.5
5	HadGEM2-ES	RCA4	
6	MPI-ESM-LR	REMO2009	

To perform climate scenario runs with the SWAP model, in total 1260 SWAP meteorological input files will be prepared for each of the case study fields. For this, an R-code will be provided, that will transfer the data files available on ZENODO into SWAP input files.

The number of SWAP input files is calculated as follows:

Reference period:

6 GCM-RCM runs x 30 years (1981-2010) ==> 180 input files

Future climate:

6 GCM-RCM runs x 3 RCPs x 2 times 30 years ==> 1080 input files

Scripts are being developed to run the pre-calibrated SWAP model with all the 1260 meteorological input files and to analyse the model results with respect to water balance elements. Changes in surface runoff, drainage outflow, soil water regime and transpiration as a crop yield indicator will be evaluated with respect to the reference period. Uncertainty in climate change predictions will be represented by the GCM-RCM combinations in the scenario analyses.

7.2. Implementation of NSWORMs in the SWAP model

SWAP is a profile-based model, with a spatial validity from profile to field scale. The spatial limitations of the SWAP model determine the NSWORMs that can be introduced in the model. Those are predominantly the so-called conservation practices, carried out by the farmers aiming at:

- Protecting soils from various types of soil degradation
- Increasing soil water retention
- Maintaining crop yields
- Improving the quality of runoff water coming from agricultural fields

These conservation practices commonly consist of soil management (reduced tillage or no-till approaches), crop rotations, crop management, fertilization types, application & timing, and amounts.

Table 7 gives an overview of the management measures applied in the field-scale model in OPTAIN and shows, for which case studies they are relevant.

Some measures can be introduced in the SWAP model directly, using specific parameters. The indirect way of incorporating an NSWORM in the SWAP model means that expert assessment is needed to select the measure-specific parameters and estimate their changes when accounting for the effects of a particular measure. Apart from land use changes - afforestation in our case - structural measures cannot be incorporated in the field-scale soil hydrological models like SWAP.

To introduce a measure in the SWAP model, soil, crop or drainage parameters or their combinations must be modified/adjusted. Figure 21 demonstrates the decision scheme on input file and parameter type selection, depending on the type of the measure.

Table 7. List of OPTAIN measures introduced in the SWAP model in different case studies

Management measures			CH	CZ	HU	LT	NO	PL
			WBF	VUMOP	ATK	KU	NIBIO	WUL
Tillage								
A06	No till agriculture	direct seeding	CS_2	CS_12				
		no tillage in autumn				CS_8	CS_10	
		no-till agriculture			CS_11			
A07	Low till agriculture	subsoiling						CS_4
		deep tillage						CS_4
		conservation tillage			CS_11	CS_8		CS_4
Other								
	Resistant plants	mulching						CS_4
		drought resistant plants	CS_2		CS_3a			
Cropping								
A03	Crop rotation	crop rotation		CS_12	CS_6			
A05	Intercropping	grain legumes intercropped with cereals & partners	CS_2					
A08	Green cover	green cover in vineyard			CS_3a			
		green cover of arable land			CS_6			
A09	Early sowing	early sowing				CS_8	CS_10	

In the OPTAIN deliverable 2.3 (Marval et al., 2022) we give a detailed overview on how to implement the key measures from Table 7 in the SWAP model and which of the model parameters should be modified. We also give approximate values on how the key parameters should be changed. The following measures are discussed in details:

- Afforestation (short- and long-term effects)
- Tillage adjustment
- Cropping adjustment
- Introducing drought-resistant plants

For each pilot field, the pre-calibrated SWAP model will be executed for each of the relevant management measures separately and in their reasonable combinations. The effects of measures on soil heat regime and water balance elements will be evaluated individually and in combinations.

Though, structural measures (like vegetation buffer zones, grassed waterways or constructed wetlands) cannot be implemented in the SWAP model, some management measures can be represented in a more sophisticated way compared to the SWAT+ model. This specifically concerns the effects of various tillage practices, mulching and land use changes on soil hydraulic properties and macropore structure, and, consequently, the water regime and soil water retention.

Figure 21. Decision scheme on input file selection for designing measures in the SWAP model

7.3. Combined scenario analyses

Combined scenario analyses will be performed by running the SWAP model with management scenario setups for all the meteorological input files representing future and reference climate.

The scenario results will be evaluated with respect to soil water balance elements, including:

- surface and subsurface (drainage) runoff and their ratio
- root water uptake
- transpiration -precipitation ratio
- plant available water during the vegetation period.

The NSWORMs will be evaluated with respect to their efficiency to reduce surface runoff, increase soil water retention and increase the amount of plant available water during droughts. For this, specific guidelines will be prepared and implemented.

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9. Appendixes

Appendix 1. Model evaluation using the benchmark criteria – Relevance

Please, give your scores (0, 1 or 2) within the red frame only.
We appreciate any additional comments in columns M-P.

		Model_1	Model_n	Good (2)	Adequate (1)	Inadequate (0)	
1. MODEL APPLICABILITY AND RELEVANCE FOR THE MANAGEMENT TASK							
1.1	How well does the model's output relate to the management task?			at least 2 items	if valid	at least 1 item	<p>the model's output can be directly related to the "core" of the management task</p> <p>the model's output (relevant to the management task) consists of variables that are commonly applied and easy to measure and quantify</p> <p>the model allows the simulation of a variety of relevant management operations</p> <p>the model's output can relate to the management task via clear, well-known, and well-established links</p> <p>the model's output is peripheral in relations to the management task</p> <p>the links between the model's output and management task are not clear or</p>
1.2	How well does the model's span and resolution in time and space compare with the requirements of the management task?			all items	if valid	if valid	<p>the model can be run with any desired spatial and temporal resolution</p> <p>the model can be run over the desired spatial and temporal span (e.g. It allows simulations to be run over many years)</p> <p>there are restrictions on the model's spatio- temporal resolution or span, but the model is expected to produce useful and meaningful results for the management task</p> <p>the model's spatial and temporal resolution or span cannot be chosen to be appropriate for the management task</p>
1.3	How well has the model been tested?			at least 3 items	at least 2 items	at least 1 item	<p>there are at least 10 documented previous model applications</p> <p>at least five model applications are published in peer-reviewed journals</p> <p>the model has been evaluated against independent data sets</p> <p>the model has been evaluated in various conditions or geographical regions</p> <p>some previous model use and evaluation is closely related to the management task in question</p> <p>there are at least three reported model applications</p> <p>the model has been evaluated in different conditions or geographical regions</p> <p>the model is specific to the site of the management task</p> <p>the model is site-specific to other type of site than that of the management task and it has not been evaluated in different conditions or geographical regions</p> <p>there are less than three documented previous model applications</p>
1.4	How complicated is the model in relation to the management task?			if valid	on of the items	on of the items	<p>the model has an optimally simple structure, i.e., it includes mostly only those processes and parameters that are known to be relevant for the management task.</p> <p>the model has a somewhat too complicated structure, i.e., most of the model's processes and parameters are relevant, but the model seemingly includes also some irrelevant processes and parameters</p> <p>its alternatively, the model is somewhat too simple, i.e. relevance to the management task could be enhanced somewhat (but not radically) by introducing some additional processes</p> <p>the model is too complex, and most of the model's features could clearly be omitted or simplified (or a more simple model could be chosen) without loss in model relevance for the management task</p> <p>alternatively, model is too simple, and many key processes relevant to the management task are not included</p>
1.5	How is the balance between the model's input data requirements and data availability?			if valid	if valid	if valid	<p>the required model input data are available from monitoring and field observations, either from the management site or from other applicable site close to it</p> <p>most of the required model input data are available from monitoring and field observations, either from the management site or from other applicable site close to it; however, some surrogate input data (e.g. results from other models, or data from other sites) must be used</p> <p>majority of the required model input data are not available from monitoring and field observations from the management site (or from other applicable site close to it)</p>
1.6	How is the identifiability of the model parameters?			at least 1 item	if valid	if valid	<p>all relevant model parameter values are well documented in scientific literature or can be estimated directly based on available data available data (corresponding to model output variables) will allow establishment of all relevant model parameter values via model calibration</p> <p>there seems to be enough data or documentation available to allow an adequate estimate of most of the relevant model parameter values (either directly or via model calibration)</p> <p>there are clearly not enough calibration data or other parameter documentation available to allow for an adequate establishment of many of the relevant model parameter values</p>
1.7	How easily are the model results understood and interpreted?			if valid	if valid	at least 1 item	<p>non-specialist users are generally capable of understanding and interpreting the model output results</p> <p>assistance from research staff or modelling specialists is necessary to clarify and interpret the model's output results</p> <p>expert skills, long experience, and deep insight (e.g., those of a model developer) are needed to understand and interpret the model results much "tacit" (i.e., difficult-to-express) knowledge or intuition is involved in the interpretation of the model results.</p>
1.8	How is the peer acceptance for the model and the model's consistency with scientific theory?			at least 2 items	at least 1 item	at least 1 item	<p>the model has gained wide and international acceptance among the scientific community</p> <p>the model is widely used in many countries</p> <p>the whole model is based on well-established scientific theory</p> <p>the model is used and gained peer-acceptance mostly locally/nationally</p> <p>most of the model components are based on well-established science</p> <p>the model is based on speculative or immature scientific theory and/or assumptions</p> <p>the model is used only by few persons</p>
Total score		0	0				
Number of "0" scores		0	0				

Appendix 2. Model evaluation using the benchmark criteria – Sensitivity

	Model_1	Model_n	Good (2)	Adequate (1)	Inadequate (0)	
Please, give your scores (0, 1 or 2) within the red frame only. We appreciate any additional comments in columns M-P.						
Items for taking decision						
2. HOW WELL IS THE MODEL SUITED FOR SENSITIVITY AND UNCERTAINTY ANALYSES AND HOW WELL HAVE THESE ANALYSES BEEN PERFORMED AND DOCUMENTED?						
2	How well is the model suited for sensitivity and uncertainty analyses and how well have these analyses been performed and documented?		at least 3 items	at least 1 item	if valid	<p>Thorough analysis of model sensitivity has been performed and reported</p> <p>model sensitivity analyses is published in peer-reviewed journal(s)</p> <p>a variety of sensitivity/uncertainty analysis techniques or software can easily and with reasonable effort be applied to the model</p> <p>the model software contains tools for sensitivity/uncertainty analysis</p> <p>uncertainty ranges, associated with the model parameter values, can be adequately established</p> <p>screening of the most sensitive model parameters has been done and published in technical report(s)</p> <p>sensitivity/uncertainty analysis techniques or software can be applied to the model, but this will be a rather laborious task</p> <p>no model sensitivity analyses has been performed because the model is generally not suitable for adequate analysis of sensitivity/uncertainty</p>
Total score			0	0		
Number of "0" scores			0	0		

Appendix 4. Outcome of the model's evaluation procedure

		MODEL NAME				
		Model_1	Model_2	Model_3	Model_4	Model_5
3	Total score					
4	Number of "0" scores					
6	Total score	RELEVANCE				
7		SensAnal				
8		Ease of Use				
10	Number of "0" scores	RELEVANCE				
11		SensAnal				
12		Ease of Use				
15	Expertise of the expert, completing the table in various models					
17	(please, give a score from 1 to 5)					
18	5	experienced in using the model				
19	4	has applied the model for 1 or 2 sites				
20	3	has limited experience with the model				
21	2	has seen papers/presentations about the model application				
22	1	heard about the model for the first time				

Appendix 5. SWAP crop input file for running the simple crop routine

```

*****
* Filename: weaths.CRP
* Contents: SWAP 4.X - Crop data of simple model
*****
* Comment area:
* Demo run SWAP, crop data - Spring barley
*****

*** PLANT GROWTH SECTION ***

*****
* Part 1: Crop development

IDEV = 1 ! length of crop cycle: 1 = fixed, 2 = variable

* If fixed growth length (IDEV = 1), specify:
LCC = 147 ! Length of the crop cycle [1..366 days, I]

* If variable growth length (IDEV = 2), specify:
TSUMEA = 1050.0 ! Temperature sum from emergence to anthesis [0..10000 C, R]
TSUMAM = 1000.0 ! Temperature sum from anthesis to maturity [0..10000 C, R]
TBASE = 0.0 ! Start value of temperature sum [-10..30 C, R]
*****

*****
* Part 2: Light extinction

KDIF = 0.6 ! Extinction coefficient for diffuse visible light [0..2 -, R]
KDIR = 0.75 ! Extinction coefficient for direct visible light [0..2 -, R]
*****

*****
* Part 3: Leaf area index or soil cover fraction

SWGCG = 1 ! choice between LAI [=1] or soil cover fraction [=2]

* If SWGCG = 1, list leaf area index [0..12 ha/ha, R], as function of dev. stage [0..2 -,R]:
* If SWGCG = 2, list soil cover fraction [0..1 m2/m2, R], as function of dev. stage [0..2 -,R]:

* DVS LAI or SCF ( maximum 36 records)
GCTB =
0.0000 0.20 ! Leaf Area Index [ha/ha]
1.0000 4.00 ! as a function of development stage of the crop [-]
2.0000 0.50

* End of table
*****

*****
* Part 4: crop factor or crop height

SWCF = 2 ! choice between crop factor [=1] or crop height [=2]
* Choose crop factor if ETref is used, either from meteo input file (SWETR = 1) or with Penman-Monteith
* Choose crop height if Penman-Monteith should be used with actual crop height, albedo and resistance

* If SWCF = 1, list crop factor CF [0.5..1.5, R], as function of dev. stage DVS [0..2 -,R]:
* If SWCF = 2, list crop height CH [0..1000 cm, R], as function of dev. stage DVS [0..2 -,R]:
* (maximum 36 records)

DVS CH CF
0.0000 0.0 0.10

```

```
1.0000 0.0 0.80
2.0000 0.0 0.80
```

* End of table

* If SWCF = 2, in addition to crop height list crop specific values for:

```
ALBEDO = 0.23 ! crop reflection coefficient [0..1.0 -, R]
RSC = 70.0 ! Minimum canopy resistance [0..10^6 s/m, R]
RSW = 2.0 ! Canopy resistance of intercepted water [0..1d6 s/m, R]
```

```
*****
*****
```

* Part 5: rooting depth

* List rooting depth [0..1000 cm, R], as a function of development stage [0..2 -,R]:

* DVS RD (maximum 36 records)

```
RDTB =
0.0000 10.0
1.0000 160.0
2.0000 160.0
```

* End of table

```
*****
*****
```

* Part 6: yield response

* List yield response factor [0.5 -,R], as function of development stage [0..2 -,R]:

* DVS KY (maximum 36 records)

```
KYTB =
0.0000 1.0
2.0000 1.0
```

* End of table

```
*****
*****
```

* Part 7: soil water extraction by plant roots

*

```
swroottyp = 1 ! Switch for type root water extraction [1,2 -, I]
! (1 = Feddes et al., 1978; 2 = De Jong van Lier et al., 2006)
```

* if swroottyp=1 then enter HLIM1 - ADCRL

* if swroottyp=2 then enter wiltpoint, rootradius, rootcoefa

*

```
HLIM1 = 0.00 ! No water extraction at higher pressure heads, [-100..100 cm, R]
HLIM2U = -1.00 ! h above which upt. red. starts for top layer, [-1000..100 cm, R]
HLIM2L = -1.00 ! h above which upt. red.starts for sub layer, [-1000..100 cm, R]
HLIM3H = -700.00 ! h below which upt. red. starts at high Tpot, [-10000..100 cm, R]
HLIM3L = -1000.00 ! h below which upt. red. starts at low Tpot, [-10000..100 cm, R]
HLIM4 = -16000.00 ! No water extraction at lower pressure heads, [-16000..100 cm, R]
ADCRH = 0.5 ! Level of high atmospheric demand, [0..5 cm/d, R]
ADCRL = 0.1 ! Level of low atmospheric demand, [0..5 cm/d, R]
```

```
*****
*****
```

* Part 8: salt stress

```
ECMAX = 2.0 ! ECsat level at which salt stress starts, [0..20 dS/m, R]
ECSLOP = 0.0 ! Decline of rootwater uptake above ECMAX [0..40 %/dS/m, R]
```

```
*****
*****
```

* Part 9: interception

SWINTER = 1 ! Switch for rainfall interception method:
 ! 0 = No interception calculated
 ! 1 = Agricultural crops (Von Hoyningen-Hune and Braden)
 ! 2 = Closed forest canopies (Gash)

* In case of interception method for agricultural crops (SWINTER = 1) specify:
 COFAB = 0.25 ! Interception coefficient Von Hoyningen-Hune and Braden, [0..1 cm, R]

* In case of interception method for closed forest canopies (SWINTER = 2) specify as function

* of time of the year T [0..366 d, R], maximum 36 records:

* PFREE = free throughfall coefficient, [0.d0..1.d0 -, R]

* PSTEM = stem flow coefficient, [0.d0..1.d0 -, R]

* SCANOPY = storage capacity of canopy, [0.d0..10.d0 cm, R]

* AVPREC = average rainfall intensity, [0.d0..100.d0 cm, R]

* AVEVAP = average evaporation intensity during rainfall from a wet canopy, [0.d0..10.d0 cm, R]

T	PFREE	PSTEM	SCANOPY	AVPREC	AVEVAP
0.0	0.9	0.05	0.4	6.0	1.5
365.0	0.9	0.05	0.4	6.0	1.5

* End of table

* Part 10: Root density distribution and root growth

* List relative root density [0..1 -, R], as function of rel. rooting depth [0..1 -, R]:

* Rdepth Rdensity (maximum 11 records)

RDCTB =
 0.000 1.0
 1.000 0.0

* End of table

*** IRRIGATION SCHEDULING SECTION ***

* Part 1: General

SCHEDULE = 0 ! Switch for application irrigation scheduling [Y=1, N=0]

* If SCHEDULE = 0, no more information is required in this input file!

* If SCHEDULE = 1, continue

STARTIRR = 30 3 ! Specify day and month after which irrigation scheduling is allowed [dd mm]

CIRRS = 0.0 ! solute concentration of scheduled irrig. water, [0..100 mg/cm³, R]

ISUAS = 1 ! Switch for type of irrigation method:

! 0 = sprinkling irrigation

! 1 = surface irrigation

* Part 2: Irrigation time criteria

* Choose one or a combination of the following 5 timing options:

*** Daily stress ***

TCS1 = 1 ! Switch, criterion Daily Stress, [Y=1, N=0]

* If TCS1 = 1, specify minimum of ratio actual/potential transpiration Trel [0..1, R],
 * as function of development stage DVS_tc1 [0..2, R], maximum 7 records:

DVS_tc1 Trel
 0.0 0.95
 2.0 0.95

* End of table

*** Depletion of Readily Available Water ***

TCS2 = 0 ! Switch, criterion Depletion of Readily Available Water, [Y=1, N=0]

* If TCS2 = 1, specify minimal fraction of readily available water RAW [0..1, R],
 * as function of development stage DVS_tc2 [0..2, R], maximum 7 records:

DVS_tc2 RAW
 0.0 0.95
 2.0 0.95

* End of table

*** Depletion of Totally Available Water ***

TCS3 = 0 ! Switch, criterion Depletion of Totally Available Water, [Y=1, N=0]

* If TCS3 = 1, specify minimal fraction of totally available water TAW [0..1, R],
 * as function of development stage DVS_tc3 [0..2, R], maximum 7 records:

DVS_tc3 TAW
 0.0 0.50
 2.0 0.50

* End of table

*** Depletion Water Amount ***

TCS4 = 0 ! Switch, criterion Depletion Water Amount, [Y=1, N=0]

* If TCS4 = 1, specify maximum amount of water depleted below field cap. DWA [0..500 mm, R],
 * as function of development stage DVS_tc4 [0..2, R], maximum 7 records:

DVS_tc4 DWA
 0.0 40.0
 2.0 40.0

* End of table

*** Pressure head or Moisture content ***

TCS5 = 0 ! Switch, criterion pressure head or moisture content, [Y=1, N=0]

* If TCS5 = 1, specify:

PHORMC = 0 ! Switch, use pressure head (PHORMC=0) or water content (PHORMC=1)
 DCRIT = -30.0! Depth of the sensor [-100..0 cm, R]

* Also specify critical pressure head [-1.d6..-100 cm, R] or moisture content
 * [0..1.0 cm3/cm3, R], as function of development stage DVS_tc5 [0..2, R]:

DVS_tc5 Value_tc5
 0.0 -1000.0
 2.0 -1000.0

* End of table

* Part 3: Irrigation depth criteria

* Choose one of the following 2 options:

*** Back to Field Capacity ***

DCS1 = 1 ! Switch, criterion Back to Field Capacity, [Y=1, N=0]

* If DCS1 = 1, specify amount of under (-) or over (+) irrigation dI [-100..100 mm, R],
* as function of development stage DVS_dc1 [0..2, R], maximum 7 records:

DVS_dc1 dI
0.0 10.0
2.0 10.0

* End of table

*** Fixed Irrigation Depth ***

DCS2 = 0 ! Switch, criterion Fixed Irrigation Depth, [Y=1, N=0]

* If DCS2 = 1, specify fixed irrigation depth FID [0..400 mm, R],
* as function of development stage DVS_dc2 [0..2, R], maximum 7 records:

DVS_dc2 FID
0.0 60.0
2.0 60.0

* End of table

* End of .crp file !

Appendix 6. Practical guidelines for using the OPTAIN manual hard calibration tool

Creating the MHC folder structure

STEP_1. The MHC folder with the R-script

sk (C:) > Users > Public > SWAP_Tools > UFZDEMO

Name	Date modified	Type	Size
SWAP_R_Calibration_Tetves	12/07/2022 18:21	File folder	
Swap_Calibration_Lite.R	27/07/2022 23:29	R File	19 KB

STEP_2. The MHC sub-folders

Users > Public > SWAP_Tools > UFZDEMO > SWAP_R_Calibration_Tetves

Name	Date modified	Type	Size
observed	12/07/2022 12:07	File folder	
plots	12/07/2022 12:07	File folder	
results	27/07/2022 23:29	File folder	
runs	27/07/2022 23:29	File folder	
SWAP	27/07/2022 23:29	File folder	
.RData	12/07/2022 18:21	R Workspace	281 KB
.Rhistory	12/07/2022 18:21	RHISTORY File	2 KB
beale.out	12/07/2022 16:57	OUT File	1 KB

STEP_3. The structure of the SWAP folder with the SWAP input files

The *.swp file is kept in the main SWAP folder, while the other (crop, draiange and meteorological) input files are copied in the corresponding sub-folders.

Name	Date modified	Type	Size
crop	12/07/2022 12:07	File folder	
drain	12/07/2022 12:07	File folder	
meteo	12/07/2022 12:07	File folder	
run_swap.cmd	21/06/2022 10:20	Windows Comma...	1 KB
Swap.exe	17/02/2022 11:43	Application	4,734 KB
Swap.swp	12/07/2022 12:19	SWP File	38 KB
swap_swap.log	27/07/2022 23:29	Text Document	1 KB

Structure of the reference data file, located within the “observed” folder

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	date	smc15	smc40	smc70				
2	10/10/2013	0.21	0.12	0.08				
3	11/10/2013	0.21	0.12	0.08				
4	12/10/2013	0.2	0.12	0.08				
5	13/10/2013	0.22	0.12	0.08				
6	14/10/2013	0.19	0.12	0.08				
7	15/10/2013	0.17	0.12	0.08				
8	16/10/2013	0.17	0.12	0.08				
9	17/10/2013	0.17	0.12	0.08				
10	18/10/2013	0.17	0.12	0.08				
11	19/10/2013	0.16	0.12	0.08				
12	20/10/2013	0.16	0.12	0.08				
13	21/10/2013	0.16	0.12	0.08				
14	22/10/2013	0.16	0.12	0.08				
15	23/10/2013	0.15	0.12	0.08				
16	24/10/2013	0.15	0.12	0.08				
17	25/10/2013	0.15	0.12	0.08				
18	26/10/2013	0.15	0.12	0.08				
19	27/10/2013	0.14	0.12	0.08				
20	28/10/2013	0.14	0.12	0.08				
21	29/10/2013	0.14	0.12	0.08				
22	30/10/2013	0.14	0.12	0.08				
23	31/10/2013	0.13	0.12	0.08				
24	01/11/2013	0.13	0.12	0.08				
25	02/11/2013	0.13	0.12	0.08				
26	03/11/2013	0.13	0.12	0.08				
27	04/11/2013	0.18	0.12	0.08				

Appendix 7. Batch File to run SWAP model and postprocessor

```
@echo off
PATH C:\pest_swap
Swap.exe
C:\Users\cucel\AppData\Local\Programs\Python\Python310\Python.exe OF.py
set /p OF=<.\pf_modeloutputOF.txt
echo CURRENT NSE VALUE is %OF%
```

Appendix 8. Cross-checking and harmonisation of the SWAP – SWAT+ model parameters

Parameter type and parameters description	SWAP	SWAT+	SWAP	SWAT+	SWAP	SWAT+
			HRU_1	HRU_2	HRU_1	HRU_2
Soil parameters						
clay content	+	+				
sand	+	+				
silt	+	+				
rock fragment content	(-)	+				
soil moist albedo	-	+				
organic matter	+	+				
bulk density	-	+				
Soil hydraulic properties						
saturated water content, Θ_s	+	-				
field capacity, Θ_{FC}	+	-				
residual water content, Θ_{RES}	+	-				
Measured values of soil water retention curve	+	-				
van Genuchten alpha	+	-				
van Genuchten n	+	-				
van Genuchten m=1-1/n	+	-				
wilting point	+	-				
available water capacity, $\Theta_{AV} = \Theta_{FC} - \Theta_{RES}$	-	+				
ratio of total to available water in soil = Θ_s / Θ_{AV}	-	-				
saturated hydraulic cond., vertical	+	+				
saturated hydraulic cond. Lateral	-	-				
saturated hydraulic cond., matrix	+	-				
maximum infiltration rate (mm/day)	-	-				
Crack/bypass flow	+	+				
	(inactive)	(inactive)				
Winter: snow						
MeltCoefAirTemp	+	-	2 (F); 4(A)		2 (F); 4(A)	
Temperature, above which all precipitation is rain	+	-	2		2	
Specific heat capacity due to freeze /thaw	-	-				
Rain/snow dividing temperature (deg C)	+	+	0	0	0	0
Soil thermal conductivity coefficient	+	-	0.61		0.61	
Thermal conductivity coefficient b (W/m deg C)	-	-				
Thermal conductivity coefficient a (W/m deg C)	-	-				
Water retention capacity of snow	+	-	0.07		0.07	
Snow pack temperature lag factor	-	+		1		1
Snowfall temperature	-	+		1		1
Snow melt base temperature	-	+		1.5		1.5
Maximum melt rate for snow	-	+		4.5		4.5
Minimum melt rate for snow	-	+		4.5		4.5
Snow melt degree-day coefficient (mm/dd-deg C)	-	-				
Water equivalent of snow	calculated	-	calculated		calculated	
Diurnal phase lag of air temperature (deg)	-	-				
Density of (new) snow (kg / m3)	calculated	+	calculated	100	calculated	100
Critical ice content above which infiltration stops (cm3/cm3)	-	-				
Winter: frost						
FreezepointF0	+	-				
FreezepointF1	+	-				
FreezepointFW1	+	-				
Unfrozen water content as a function of temperature	-	-				

Parameter type and parameters description	SWAP	SWAT+	SWAP	SWAT+	SWAP	SWAT+
			HRU_1		HRU_2	
Surface runoff/storage or surface water management						
The maximum surface pool cover - SPMaxCover	+	-				
The potential surface cover - SPCovPot	+	-				
Amount of water on the surface at complete soil cover - SPCoverTotal	+	-				
Surface runoff (from surface pool) coefficient - SurfCoef	+	-	0.8		0.8	
Max amount of water stored in the surface without runoff(cm)	+	-	0.5		0.5	
Kirkham's depth for flow to drains (cm)	-	-				
Surface runoff lag time (day)	-	+		0.5(F); 0.2(A)		0.5(F); 0.2(A)
Curve number	-	+				
Manning's n value for overland flow	-	+				
Curve number calculation methods	-	+				
Interception						
WaterCapacityBase	+	-	0		0	
WaterCapacityPerLAI	+	-	0.2		0.2	
Maximum canopy storage	-	+		0		0
Transpiration						
CanDensMax	+	-	0.7		0.7	
CondMax	+	-	0.02		0.02	
CondRis	+	-	5.0 E6		5.0 E6	
CondVPD	+	-	100		100	
RoughLMin	+	-	0.01		0.01	
WindLessExchangeCanopy	+	-	0.001		0.001	
Lower limit of water content in the root zone (cm3 / cm3)	-	-				
Limiting water table (cm)	-	-				
Plant uptake compensation factor	-	+		0		0
Evaporation						
Penman surface resistance parameter - psiRs_1p	+	-	200		200	
LAI contribution to aerodynamic resistance - RaiIncreaseWithLAI	+	-	50		50	
Surface roughness length for bare soil - RoughLBareSoilMom	+	-	0.001		0.001	
Calculate sublimation Yes/NO	-	+		yes		yes
Soil evaporation compensation factor - ESCO	-	+		0		0
Crop parameters						
growth season starting date	-	-				
growth period	-	-				
growth curve offset	-	-				
growth curve amplitude	-	-				
maximum rooting depth	+	+	driving variable	1(A); 2(F)	driving variable	1(A); 2(F)
root distribution	time series	-	Table 5		Table 5	
canopy height	time series	-				
LAI	time series	-				
displacement height	f(canopy)	-				
roughness	f(canopy)	-				
albedo	+	-	25(A); 9(F)		25(A); 9(F)	
Plant uptake compensation factor - EPCO	-	+		0		0
Temperatur sum to maturity	-	+				

Parameter type and parameters description	SWAP	SWAT+	SWAP	SWAT+	SWAP	SWAT+
			HRU_1		HRU_2	
Groundwater						
Maximum groundwater effective depth (m)	-	-				
Proportion of filled pore space	-	-				
GWSourceFlow	+	-				
GWSourceLayer	+	-				
Groundwater delay	-	+		5		5
base flow recession constant	-	+				
deep percolation fraction	-	+		0		0
groundwater revaporation coef.	-	+		0.02		0.02
Water uptake						
CritThresholdDry	+	-	2000(A); 400(F)		2000(A); 400(F)	
DemandRelCoef	+	-	0.3		0.3	
FlexibilityDegree	+	-	0.6		0.6	
Subsurface / Drainage						
Distance from surface to impermeable layer						
Depth from drain to permeable layer	-	-				
Depth from surface to impermeable layer (m)	-	+		2		2
Drainage coefficient (cm/day)	-	-				
Kirkham's coefficient	-	-				
Time to drain the soil to field capacity (hours)	-	+		24		24
Drain tile lag time (hours)	-	+		12		12
Land phase parameters						
Coef. for storage time constant of normal flow	-	+				
Coef. for storage time constant of low flow	-	+				
Lateral flow travel time	-	+		2(F); 1(A)		2(F); 1(A)
Maximum soil moisture deficit	-	-				
Reach parameters						
Parameter controlling water storage in reach	-	+				
Parameter controlling reach evaporation	-	+				
Manning's coefficient	-	+		0.014		0.014
Channel width/depth ratio	-	+		13.4		13.4
Effective hydraulic conductivity in the main channel alluvium	-	+		1		1
base flow index	-	+		0.17		0.17
Minimum water temperature	-	-				
Flow parameter a	-	-				
Flow parameter b	-	-				